

GREEN SCENT

SMART CITIZEN EDUCATION
FOR A GREEN FUTURE

Project Start Date: 1 January 2022 | Duration: 36 months

D5.3 – GreenSCENT Pilot Implementation and Validation Report (*Update*)

This report, D5.3u, is an update of the original deliverable, D5.3, providing additional information on the implementation of demonstrator activities. D5.3u differs from D5.3 in two respects. First, Section 11.9 in D5.3 (including the summary statistics table, which is also updated) is re-numbered as Section 11.10 in D5.3u. Second, D5.3u includes a new section 11.9 with the additional information.

Due Date of the Updated Deliverable D5.3u: 31 December 2024 (project end)

Actual Submission Date of the Updated Deliverable D5.3u: 31 December 2024

Due Date of the Deliverable D5.3: 31 October 2024 (extension of former 30 April 2024 accepted by PO)

Actual Submission Date of the Deliverable D5.3: 31 October 2024

Project	GreenSCENT – Smart Citizen Education for a Green Future
Call ID	H2020-LC-GD-2020-3-2020
Work Package	WP5 – GreenComp Piloting
Work Package Leader	University of Novi Sad Faculty of Sciences (UNSPMF)
Deliverable Leader	Climate Risk Analysis – Manfred Mudelsee (CRA)
Deliverable Coordinator	Manfred Mudelsee (CRA)
Deliverable Type	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Version	Final 16 (13 December 2024)
Revision	Draft

Content

ACRONYMS.....	9
1. DOCUMENT INFORMATION	11
1.1 AUTHOR.....	11
1.2 CONTRIBUTORS	11
1.3 REVIEWERS.....	12
1.4 DOCUMENT HISTORY.....	12
1.5 DOCUMENT DATA.....	13
2. BACKGROUND	14
2.1 EUROPEAN GREEN DEAL	14
2.2 GREENSCENT	14
2.3 THIS DOCUMENT	15
3. WHAT ARE THE DEMONSTRATORS?.....	16
4. WHAT ARE THE PILOTS?.....	16
5. WHO ARE THE STAKEHOLDERS?.....	16
6. GREENSCENT PILOT WORKSHOPS	16
7. ROLES OF THE PARTNERS.....	16
8. ETHICS AND PRIVACY.....	17
9. CHALLENGES, RISKS AND MITIGATION ACTIONS.....	18
10. DEMONSTRATORS	21
10.1 ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING APP (ENG)	21
10.2 CITIZEN JOURNALISM/GREENVERSE (ENG).....	21
10.3 INTERACTIVE DOCUMENTARY/GREENVERSE (ENG)	21
10.4 MICROPLASTIC CITIZEN SCIENCE (UAB)	21
10.5 OPEN INNOVATION (AGO).....	21
10.6 CLIMATHON (CRA)	21
10.7 CLEANAIR@SCHOOLS (4S)	21
10.8 GREENSCENT AUGMENTED REALITY APP (BSC)	21
10.9 YOUTH DESIGN ASSEMBLIES (DEMOCRACY X)	21
11. PILOT IMPLEMENTATIONS	22
11.1 PILOT PARTNER UAB (ES).....	22
11.1.1 <i>Demonstrator Activity GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App</i>	22
11.1.1.1 Technology Relevance	22
11.1.1.2 Implementation Statistics.....	22
11.1.1.3 Ethical Questions.....	22
11.1.1.4 Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update	22
11.1.1.5 User Experience.....	22
11.1.1.6 Cross-Cultural Impact	22
11.1.2 <i>Demonstrator Activity Youth Design Assemblies</i>	22
11.1.2.1 Technology Relevance.....	22
11.1.2.2 Implementation Statistics.....	23

11.1.2.3	Ethical Questions.....	23
11.1.2.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	23
11.1.2.5	User Experience.....	23
11.1.2.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	24
11.2	PILOT PARTNER EA (GR)	24
11.2.1	<i>Demonstrator Activity Environmental Monitoring App</i>	24
11.2.1.1	Technology Relevance.....	24
11.2.1.2	Implementation Statistics.....	24
11.2.1.3	Ethical Questions.....	24
11.2.1.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	24
11.2.1.5	User Experience.....	24
11.2.1.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	24
11.2.2	<i>Demonstrator Activity Citizen Journalism/Greenverse</i>	25
11.2.2.1	Technology Relevance.....	25
11.2.2.2	Implementation Statistics.....	25
11.2.2.3	Ethical Questions.....	25
11.2.2.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	25
11.2.2.5	User Experience.....	25
11.2.2.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	25
11.2.3	<i>Demonstrator Activity Interactive Documentary/Greenverse</i>	25
11.2.3.1	Technology Relevance.....	25
11.2.3.2	Implementation Statistics.....	26
11.2.3.3	Ethical Questions.....	26
11.2.3.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	26
11.2.3.5	User Experience.....	27
11.2.3.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	27
11.2.4	<i>Demonstrator Activity Microplastic Citizen Science</i>	27
11.2.4.1	Technology Relevance.....	27
11.2.4.2	Implementation Statistics.....	28
11.2.4.3	Ethical Questions.....	28
11.2.4.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	28
11.2.4.5	User Experience.....	28
11.2.4.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	28
11.2.5	<i>Demonstrator Activity Climathon</i>	28
11.2.5.1	Technology Relevance.....	28
11.2.5.2	Implementation Statistics.....	28
11.2.5.3	Ethical Questions.....	29
11.2.5.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	29
11.2.5.5	User Experience.....	29
11.2.5.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	30
11.2.6	<i>Demonstrator Activity CleanAir@Schools</i>	30
11.2.6.1	Technology Relevance.....	30
11.2.6.2	Implementation Statistics.....	31
11.2.6.3	Ethical Questions.....	33
11.2.6.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	33
11.2.6.5	User Experience.....	33
11.2.6.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	33
11.2.7	<i>Demonstrator Activity GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App</i>	34
11.2.7.1	Technology Relevance.....	34
11.2.7.2	Implementation Statistics.....	34
11.2.7.3	Ethical Questions.....	34
11.2.7.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	34
11.2.7.5	User Experience.....	35
11.2.7.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	35

11.2.8	<i>Demonstrator Activity Youth Design Assemblies</i>	35
11.2.8.1	Technology Relevance	36
11.2.8.2	Implementation Statistics	36
11.2.8.3	Ethical Questions	36
11.2.8.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update	36
11.2.8.5	User Experience	36
11.2.8.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	36
11.3	PILOT PARTNER MAYK (FI)	36
11.3.1	<i>Demonstrator Activity Environmental Monitoring App</i>	36
11.3.1.1	Technology Relevance	36
11.3.1.2	Implementation Statistics	36
11.3.1.3	Ethical Questions	37
11.3.1.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update	37
11.3.1.5	User Experience	37
11.3.1.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	37
11.3.2	<i>Demonstrator Activity CleanAir@Schools</i>	38
11.3.2.1	Technology Relevance	38
11.3.2.2	Implementation Statistics	38
11.3.2.3	Ethical Questions	38
11.3.2.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update	38
11.3.2.5	User Experience	38
11.3.2.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	38
11.3.3	<i>Demonstrator Activity GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App</i>	38
11.3.3.1	Technology Relevance	38
11.3.3.2	Implementation Statistics	38
11.3.3.3	Ethical Questions	38
11.3.3.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update	38
11.3.3.5	User Experience	38
11.3.3.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	38
11.4	PILOT PARTNER RST (RO)	38
11.4.1	<i>Demonstrator Activity Environmental Monitoring App</i>	38
11.4.1.1	Technology Relevance	38
11.4.1.2	Implementation Statistics	39
11.4.1.3	Ethical Questions	39
11.4.1.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update	39
11.4.1.5	User Experience	40
11.4.1.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	40
11.4.2	<i>Demonstrator Activity Citizen Journalism/Greenverse</i>	40
11.4.2.1	Technology Relevance	40
11.4.2.2	Implementation Statistics	40
11.4.2.3	Ethical Questions	41
11.4.2.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update	41
11.4.2.5	User Experience	41
11.4.2.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	41
11.4.3	<i>Demonstrator Activity Interactive Documentary/Greenverse</i>	41
11.4.3.1	Technology Relevance	41
11.4.3.2	Implementation Statistics	42
11.4.3.3	Ethical Questions	42
11.4.3.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update	42
11.4.3.5	User Experience	42
11.4.3.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	43
11.4.4	<i>Demonstrator Activity CleanAir@Schools</i>	43
11.4.4.1	Technology Relevance	43
11.4.4.2	Implementation Statistics	43

11.4.4.3	Ethical Questions.....	44
11.4.4.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	44
11.4.4.5	User Experience.....	44
11.4.4.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	44
11.4.5	<i>Demonstrator Activity GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App.....</i>	45
11.4.5.1	Technology Relevance.....	45
11.4.5.2	Implementation Statistics.....	45
11.4.5.3	Ethical Questions.....	45
11.4.5.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	46
11.4.5.5	User Experience.....	46
11.4.5.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	46
11.4.6	<i>Demonstrator Activity Youth Design Assemblies.....</i>	46
11.4.6.1	Technology Relevance.....	46
11.4.6.2	Implementation Statistics.....	46
11.4.6.3	Ethical Questions.....	47
11.4.6.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	47
11.4.6.5	User Experience.....	47
11.4.6.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	47
11.5	PILOT PARTNER RGSMART (RS).....	47
11.5.1	<i>Demonstrator Activity Environmental Monitoring App.....</i>	47
11.5.1.1	Technology Relevance.....	47
11.5.1.2	Implementation Statistics.....	48
11.5.1.3	Ethical Questions.....	48
11.5.1.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	48
11.5.1.5	User Experience.....	48
11.5.1.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	49
11.5.2	<i>Demonstrator Activity Citizen Journalism/Greenverse.....</i>	49
11.5.2.1	Technology Relevance.....	49
11.5.2.2	Implementation Statistics.....	49
11.5.2.3	Ethical Questions.....	50
11.5.2.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	50
11.5.2.5	User Experience.....	50
11.5.2.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	50
11.5.3	<i>Demonstrator Activity Interactive Documentary/Greenverse.....</i>	50
11.5.3.1	Technology Relevance.....	50
11.5.3.2	Implementation Statistics.....	51
11.5.3.3	Ethical Questions.....	51
11.5.3.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	51
11.5.3.5	User Experience.....	51
11.5.3.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	52
11.5.4	<i>Demonstrator Activity Climathon.....</i>	52
11.5.4.1	Technology Relevance.....	52
11.5.4.2	Implementation Statistics.....	52
11.5.4.3	Ethical Questions.....	52
11.5.4.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	53
11.5.4.5	User Experience.....	53
11.5.4.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	53
11.5.5	<i>Demonstrator Activity CleanAir@Schools.....</i>	54
11.5.5.1	Technology Relevance.....	54
11.5.5.2	Implementation Statistics.....	54
11.5.5.3	Ethical Questions.....	54
11.5.5.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	54
11.5.5.5	User Experience.....	54
11.5.5.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	54

11.5.6	<i>Demonstrator Activity GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App</i>	54
11.5.6.1	Technology Relevance	54
11.5.6.2	Implementation Statistics	55
11.5.6.3	Ethical Questions	55
11.5.6.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update	55
11.5.6.5	User Experience	55
11.5.6.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	56
11.5.7	<i>Demonstrator Activity Youth Design Assemblies</i>	56
11.5.7.1	Technology Relevance	56
11.5.7.2	Implementation Statistics	56
11.5.7.3	Ethical Questions	56
11.5.7.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update	56
11.5.7.5	User Experience	57
11.5.7.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	57
11.6	PILOT PARTNER UNINETTUNO (IT)	57
11.6.1	<i>Demonstrator Activity Environmental Monitoring App</i>	57
11.6.1.1	Technology Relevance	57
11.6.1.2	Implementation Statistics	58
11.6.1.3	Ethical Questions	58
11.6.1.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update	59
11.6.1.5	User Experience	59
11.6.1.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	60
11.6.2	<i>Demonstrator Activity Citizen Journalism/Greenverse</i>	61
11.6.2.1	Technology Relevance	61
11.6.2.2	Implementation Statistics	61
11.6.2.3	Ethical Questions	62
11.6.2.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update	62
11.6.2.5	User Experience	62
11.6.2.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	64
11.6.3	<i>Demonstrator Activity Interactive Documentary/Greenverse</i>	65
11.6.3.1	Technology Relevance	65
11.6.3.2	Implementation Statistics	65
11.6.3.3	Ethical Questions	66
11.6.3.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update	66
11.6.3.5	User Experience	66
11.6.3.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	68
11.6.4	<i>Demonstrator Activity Climathon</i>	68
11.6.4.1	Technology Relevance	69
11.6.4.2	Implementation Statistics	69
11.6.4.3	Ethical Questions	69
11.6.4.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update	69
11.6.4.5	User Experience	69
11.6.4.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	69
11.6.5	<i>Demonstrator Activity CleanAir@Schools</i>	69
11.6.5.1	Technology Relevance	69
11.6.5.2	Italy Implementation: Implementation Statistics	70
11.6.5.3	Italy Implementation: Ethical Questions	70
11.6.5.4	Italy Implementation: Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update	70
11.6.5.5	Italy Implementation: User Experience	71
11.6.5.6	Italy Implementation: Cross-Cultural Impact	74
11.6.5.7	Romania Implementation: Implementation Statistics	74
11.6.5.8	Romania Implementation: Ethical Questions	75
11.6.5.9	Romania Implementation: Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update	75
11.6.5.10	Romania Implementation: User Experience	76

11.6.5.11	Romania Implementation: Cross-Cultural Impact	77
11.6.6	<i>New, Experimental Demonstrator Activity Knowledge Graph</i>	79
11.6.6.1	Technology Relevance	79
11.6.6.2	Implementation Statistics.....	79
11.6.6.3	Ethical Questions.....	80
11.6.6.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	80
11.6.6.5	User Experience.....	80
11.6.6.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	82
11.7	PILOT PARTNER UNSPMF (RS)	83
11.7.1	<i>Demonstrator Activity Interactive Documentary/Greenverse</i>	83
11.7.1.1	Technology Relevance	83
11.7.1.2	Implementation Statistics.....	83
11.7.1.3	Ethical Questions.....	84
11.7.1.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	84
11.7.1.5	User Experience.....	84
11.7.1.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	84
11.7.2	<i>Demonstrator Activity Microplastic Citizen Science</i>	84
11.7.2.1	Technology Relevance	85
11.7.2.2	Implementation Statistics.....	85
11.7.2.3	Ethical Questions.....	85
11.7.2.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	85
11.7.2.5	User Experience.....	85
11.7.2.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	85
11.7.3	<i>Demonstrator Activity Climathon</i>	85
11.7.3.1	Technology Relevance.....	85
11.7.3.2	Implementation Statistics.....	85
11.7.3.3	Ethical Questions.....	86
11.7.3.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	86
11.7.3.5	User Experience.....	86
11.7.3.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	87
11.7.4	<i>Demonstrator Activity CleanAir@Schools</i>	87
11.7.4.1	Technology Relevance.....	87
11.7.4.2	Implementation Statistics.....	88
11.7.4.3	Ethical Questions.....	88
11.7.4.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	88
11.7.4.5	User Experience.....	88
11.7.4.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	89
11.7.5	<i>Demonstrator Activity Youth Design Assemblies</i>	89
11.7.5.1	Technology Relevance.....	89
11.7.5.2	Implementation Statistics.....	89
11.7.5.3	Ethical Questions.....	90
11.7.5.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	90
11.7.5.5	User Experience.....	90
11.7.5.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	90
11.8	PILOT PARTNER CITIZENS (EU)	90
11.8.1	<i>Demonstrator Activity Open Innovation (written by AGO)</i>	90
11.8.1.1	Technology Relevance.....	90
11.8.1.2	Implementation Statistics.....	91
11.8.1.3	Ethical Questions.....	92
11.8.1.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	92
11.8.1.5	User Experience.....	92
11.8.1.6	Cross-Cultural Impact	93
11.8.2	<i>Demonstrator Activity CleanAir@Schools (written by 4S)</i>	93
11.8.2.1	Technology Relevance.....	93

11.8.2.2	Implementation Statistics.....	94
11.8.2.3	Ethical Questions.....	95
11.8.2.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	95
11.8.2.5	User Experience.....	95
11.8.2.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	96
11.8.3	<i>Demonstrator Activity Youth Design Assemblies (written by Democracy X).....</i>	96
11.8.3.1	Technology Relevance.....	96
11.8.3.2	Implementation Statistics.....	97
11.8.3.3	Ethical Questions.....	97
11.8.3.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	97
11.8.3.5	User Experience.....	97
11.8.3.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	98
11.9	UPDATES.....	98
11.9.1	<i>Update on Section 11.8.2 (Demonstrator Activity CleanAir@Schools for Citizens (EU)): CleanAir@Schools implementation at schools in Copenhagen, Denmark (written by 4S).....</i>	98
11.9.2	<i>Update on Section 11.5.6 (Demonstrator Activity GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App implemented at RGSMART).....</i>	99
11.9.3	<i>Update on Section 11.8 (Demonstrator Activity GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App for Citizens (EU)) (written by BSC).....</i>	99
11.9.3.1	Technology Relevance.....	99
11.9.3.2	Implementation Statistics.....	100
11.9.3.3	Ethical Questions.....	100
11.9.3.4	Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update.....	100
11.9.3.5	User Experience.....	101
11.9.3.6	Cross-Cultural Impact.....	101
11.10	SUMMARY STATISTICS.....	102

Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AR	Augmented Reality
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
COVID-19	Corona Virus Disease-19
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
Dx.y	Deliverable x.y (where x and y are integer numbers between 1 and 9)
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
GA	Grant Agreement including amendment(s)
GDPR	EU's General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GIS	Geographic Information System
HEI	Higher Education Institution
iOS	iPhone Operating System
IP	Intellectual Property
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
Mbps	Megabits per second
Mxx	Project Month xx (where xx is an integer number between 1 and 36)

Acronym	Description
NA	Not Applicable
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NO ₂	Nitrogen Dioxide
OS	Operating System
PC	Personal Computer
PO	Project Officer
PSHEE	Personal, Social, Health and Economic Education
PTR	Periodic Technical Report
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SMEs	Small- and Medium-sized Enterprises
TED	Technology, Entertainment, Design
TEDx	TED event, independently organized
UN	United Nations
WP	Work Package
YDA	Youth Design Assembly

1. Document Information

1.1 Author

Author Name	Partner Organisation	Email
Manfred Mudelsee	CRA	mudelsee@climate-risk-analysis.com

1.2 Contributors

Author Name	Partner Organisation	Email
Lorena Banyuls	4S	lorena.banyuls@4sfera.com
Jaume Targa	4S	jaume.targa@4sfera.com
Solène Delarue	AGO	solene.delarue@agorize.com
Diana Urquiza	BSC	diana.urquiza@bsc.es
Martin Neureiter	CSRC	martin.neureiter@csr-company.com
Patrick Neureiter	CSRC	patrick.neureiter@csr-company.com
Gabriele Sauberer	CSRC	gabriele.sauberer@csr-company.com
Mark Hessellund Beanland	Democracy X	mhb@demx.dk
Ditte Burmeister	Democracy X	db@demx.dk
Sif Juhl Jacobsen	Democracy X	sjj@demx.dk
Thomas Ratje	Democracy X	trr@demx.dk
Loukas Katikas	EA	lkatikas@ea.gr
Thomas Oikonomou	EA	thoikonomou@ea.gr
Jana Faschinger-Sanborn	ECQA	Jana_Faschinger-Sanborn@ecqa.org
Michael Reiner	ECQA	ecqa_ceo@ecqa.org
Vladimiro Scotto Di Carlo	ENG	Vladimiro.ScottodiCarlo@eng.it
Elisa Mehtälä	MAYK	Elisa.Mehtala@mayk.fi
Nora Pircklén	MAYK	Nora.Pircklen@mayk.fi
Jelena Desnica	RGSMART	jelena.desnica@smart.edu.rs
Anda Bădită	RST	anda.lup@royalschool.ro
Joe Berwick	RST	head@royalschool.ro

Author Name	Partner Organisation	Email
Sarah McDonagh	UAB	sarahanne.mcdonagh@uab.cat
Pilar Orero	UAB	Pilar.Orero@uab.cat
Allesandro Caforio	UNINETTUNO	alessandro.caforio@uninettunouniversity.net
Gian Andrea Giacobone	UNINETTUNO	gianandrea.giacobone@uninettunouniversity.net
Vanni Resta	UNINETTUNO	vanni.resta@uninettunouniversity.net
Andrea Tomassi	UNINETTUNO	andrea.tomassi@uninettunouniversity.net
Biljana Basarin	UNSPMF	biljana.basarin@dgt.uns.ac.rs
Miroslav Vujcic	UNSPMF	miroslav.vujcic@dgt.uns.ac.rs
Zarrin Fatima	VTT	Zarrin.Fatima@vtt.fi
Teuvo Uusitalo	VTT	Teuvo.Uusitalo@vtt.fi

1.3 Reviewers

Reviewer Name	Partner Organisation	Email
Mark Hessellund Beanland	Democracy X	mhb@demx.dk
Sarah McDonagh	UAB	sarahanne.mcdonagh@uab.cat
Pilar Orero	UAB	Pilar.Orero@uab.cat

1.4 Document History

Version #	Date	Changes
0	1 February 2024	Initial template erected; internal online site for individual reports established; internal grid table (demonstrator/pilot) built
1	16 May 2024	Draft 01 based on weekly WP5 Friday Online Discussion meetings
2	29 May 2024	Draft 02 based on weekly WP5 Friday Online Discussion meetings
3	31 May 2024	Draft 03 based on weekly WP5 Friday Online Discussion meetings
4	13 June 2024	Draft 04 based on weekly WP5 Friday Online Discussion meetings

Version #	Date	Changes
5	14 June 2024	Draft 05 based on weekly WP5 Friday Online Discussion meetings; preliminary submission to internal review (Section 1.3)
5	14 June 2024	Draft 05 based on weekly WP5 Friday Online Discussion meetings; preliminary submission to internal review (Section 1.3)
6	17 July 2024	Draft 06 based on new online input
7	8 August 2024	Draft 07 based on new online input
8	29 August 2024	Draft 08 based on new online input
9	9 September 2024	Draft 09, completion of initial input, submission to internal review (Section 1.3)
10	22 October 2024	Draft 10, revised version based on received internal review comments
11	29 October 2024	Draft 11, revised version based on further discussions with reviewers
12	30 October 2024	Draft 12, revised version based on further discussions with reviewers, addition of a summary statistics table, partner organisation DBT renamed as Democracy X
13	31 October 2024	Draft 13, revised version based on further discussions with selected contributors and reviewers; this is also the final version for submission by coordinator to EC
14	27 November 2024	D5.3u copied from D5.3 (final version), first input
15	12 December 2024	Draft 15, based on input from BSC
16	13 December 2024	Draft 16 based on WP5 Friday Online Discussion meeting, updated participant numbers; this is also the final version for submission by coordinator to EC

1.5 Document Data

Keywords	<i>Behavioural Change, Climate Change, Education, Environment, Green Deal, GreenSCENT Competence Framework, Instructional Co-Design, Learning Performance, Preparatory Training, Validation</i>
Author Contact Details	Dr. Manfred Mudelsee, Chief Executive Officer Climate Risk Analysis – Manfred Mudelsee e.K. Kreuzstrasse 27, Heckenbeck 37581 Bad Gandersheim Germany Telephone: +49 5563 9998140 Email: mudelsee@climate-risk-analysis.com

2. Background

2.1 European Green Deal

As the EC [https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en, 19 June 2023] explains, climate change and environmental degradation are an existential threat to Europe and the world. To overcome these challenges, the European Green Deal will transform the EU into a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy, ensuring:

- no net emissions of greenhouse gases by 2050;
- economic growth decoupled from resource use;
- no person and no place left behind.

The European Green Deal is also our lifeline out of the Corona Virus Disease-19 (COVID-19) pandemic. One third of the €1.8 trillion investments from the NextGenerationEU Recovery Plan, and the EU's seven-year budget will finance the European Green Deal.

2.2 GreenSCENT

GreenSCENT – Smart Citizen Education for a Green Future – is a research and innovation project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under Grant Agreement N° 101036480.

GreenSCENT aims at developing a competence framework embracing all the Green Deal focus areas through an iterative, participated, experience and learning-by-doing based design approach.

GreenSCENT activities embrace both experts' and researchers' inputs and advice, citizen participation and stakeholder engagement initiatives; different European regions, different educational levels (from primary schools to higher education), at different engagement levels (from observation to data collection and processing, to contribute to scientific and policy agenda).

GreenSCENT legacy will consist of the GreenSCENT Competence Framework, its Methodology, Use Cases, User Guides; Training kits co-designed for implementing the framework; SCENTbox, the set of digital, physical and hybrid demonstrators developed by the project; and ECCEL, a European “driving license” for Climate and Environmental competencies and skills, that will be tested during the project.

GreenSCENT's Work Package WP5 – GreenComp Piloting – has the objective to develop a common piloting framework, and the application of tools and approaches for eight European Green Deal Focus Areas, that can be extended and implemented elsewhere, with the objective of creating genuine European reference piloting environments. The common piloting framework and tools will, through training, enable the involved citizens to become aware of European Green Deal principles. This WP provides input and iteratively co-develops content and activities aimed at enhancing educational, social, technical and cross-cultural impacts.

GreenSCENT's WP5 includes Task 5.2, where the main objective is to provide a plan for the operation of the demonstrator activities at the piloting institutions. The plan, delivered as D5.2, is constructed as a result of previous work in Task 5.1 (Subtasks 5.1.1 and 5.1.2). GreenSCENT's WP5 also includes Task 5.3, where the implementation of the operational plan (D5.2) is reported. Task 5.3 is planned to run until Project Month 30 (M30). The WP5 leader coordinates the development efforts in other WPs for the management of the operational plans for the SCENTbox (i.e., the set of digital and physical demonstrators developed), the GreenSCENT Competence Framework, the SCENT Platform and the GreenSCENT mobile application; the WP5 leader will also oversee the co-creation process. In WP5, the task leaders will, together with the WP5 leader, coordinate high-level implementation of strategies and plans and set or agree on goals and milestones.

2.3 This Document

This document reports on the implementation of the operational plan as part of Task 5.3. The definition of what will happen in each pilot, the general concepts, the initially proposed and co-created activities, the deployment and the KPIs – all this has already been communicated as part of D5.2. There is one exception to this statement: UNINETTUNO decided to take a tool (Knowledge Graph) that it had developed within GreenSCENT and embed it into a separate, new, experimental demonstrator activity; see Section 11.6.6.

Since this document D5.3 is so closely related to D5.2, we will explain below how it relates to D5.2, which sections are being reproduced (and why) and which are not. The references to D5.2 and the indications of whether something is reproduced in full or not: this is indicated here typographically by the use of Arial, 10 pt, bold, italics, as here in this paragraph.

We believe that in order to achieve the objectives of D5.3, it is sufficient to refer only to (but not to reproduce) the sections on the three main "actors", that means, the Demonstrators (Section 3), the Pilots (Section 4) and the Stakeholders (Section 5) targeted by the activities. Similarly, it is sufficient to mention the section on the typical generalized structure and objectives of the pilot workshops in GreenSCENT (Section 6) and the advice on the roles of the different partners involved in the educational activities (Section 7). However, as ethical issues are an important part of the final evaluation of the pilot implementation and validation, we reproduce here in full what has been written in D5.2 on Ethics (Section 8); later here in D5.3 (as a separate subsection of Section 11), ethical issues are dealt with individually for each demonstrator activity implemented at a pilot site. In addition, we repeat here the general section on project Challenges and Risks (Section 9), which will be dealt with later in D5.3 (as a separate subsection of Section 11) individually for each demonstrator activity implemented at a pilot site. As for the demonstrator activities (section 10), these are already fully described in D5.2 and need not be repeated here. Finally, the "core" of this report is a longer, more descriptive and detailed section that describes the local implementations at the pilot sites (Section 11).

3. What are the Demonstrators?

This general section on the Demonstrators from the report of the operational plan (D5.2) is not reproduced here in D5.3.

4. What are the Pilots?

This general section on the Pilots from the report of the operational plan (D5.2) is not reproduced here in D5.3.

5. Who are the Stakeholders?

This section on the Stakeholders from the report of the operational plan (D5.2) is not reproduced here in D5.3.

6. GreenSCENT Pilot Workshops

This section on the GreenSCENT Pilot Workshops from the report of the operational plan (D5.2) is not reproduced here in D5.3.

7. Roles of the Partners

This section on the Roles of the Partners from the report of the operational plan (D5.2) is not reproduced here in D5.3.

8. Ethics and Privacy

This section on Ethics and Privacy from the report of the operational plan (D5.2) is not reproduced here in D5.3. However, a clarifying paragraph is added below.

Ethical approval was sought and approved by the Ethical Committee at UAB at the beginning of this project. UAB oversees the ethics of this project, which includes piloting activities. However, all piloting partners are responsible for the administration and storage of the consent forms. The UAB ethical code for the GreenSCENT project is CEEAH: 5712.

9. Challenges, Risks and Mitigation Actions

This section on Challenges, Risks and Mitigation Actions from the report of the operational plan (D5.2) is reproduced in full here in D5.3. A remark on the "current state" mentioned in the next paragraph: this will be updated here in D5.3, Section 11 to the state at M34.

The Periodic Technical Report (PTR) about the first project half (M1 to M18), Section 6 therein, listed critical implementation risk and mitigation actions. In relation to this pilot operation plan from WP5, the following entries are relevant (Tables 1, 2). Within these tables, we also comment on the current state (M22) from our perspective in WP5.

Table 1. Foreseen risks for WP5, applied mitigation measures, comments about state at M18 from PTR and comments about state at M22 from WP5.

Risk Number	Description	Applied mitigation measures	Comments (M18)	Comments from WP5 (M22)
8	Incomplete identification of all the involved stakeholders in the different pilots and consequent failure to engage them.	The involvement of leading institutions in each pilot, with extensive knowledge and connections in their respective contexts, is expected to enable a comprehensive identification and successful engagement of all relevant stakeholders.	While, as expected, the consortium includes relevant stakeholders from school, academia, industries and research centres, GreenSCENT managed to engage with external experts and interested stakeholders also beyond the purely educational landscape, through the "stakeholder survey" managed by AGORIZE and reaching hundreds of respondents across several countries, and through communication and dissemination activities targeting citizenship at large, scientific communities, education communities beyond the project consortium, and high level events as reported in D6.8.	As regards the stakeholders for WP5 (Section 5) – primary and secondary schools, HEIs, and EU citizens –, WP5 agrees with the overall positive comments for M18. The piloting activities carried out so far for the schools (Section 11) show an engaged performance of the schools and active participation from pupils. The same is expected also for HEIs, although the current data situation is less complete here (Section 11). The engagement and approach of EU citizens by various communication tools /Section 5.4) is being continued.
9	Communication issues that derive from the diversity of actors between the consortium and the involved communities: technical and non-technical actors, with different levels of education.	In its addressing of the pilot cases, the consortium will strive to promote an inclusive environment, with regular dissemination activities/ establishing clear communication pathways on the progress and applications of the research work.	Pilots, demonstrators and research protocols summarize inputs coming from several fields of expertise: psychology, pedagogy, environmental sciences, engineering, economy, service design, accessibility and media literacy among the others. This approach allowed an integration of visions and insights and the development of a shared commitment in the consortium and among all the involved actors for developing project results and planning pilot activities.	As can be said from the weekly or bi-weekly "WP5 Friday Online Meetings", there is full agreement with the comment from M18 about the involvement and commitment by the various partners. This clear communication indeed delivers a safe mitigation measure.
11	Low level of interest in workshop and pilot participation.	Coordinator and WP leaders clearly explain the scope of GreenSCENT and invite a wide range of participants. Workshops' schedule is arranged taking into account the participants' needs and availability. GreenSCENT will also motivate participants by offering meetings with experts and incentives.	Participation in the project activities was strong and committed; the consortium managed to raise the interest about the project outside the consortium, involving other projects both in discussion and common dissemination activities, and in pilot activities. GreenSCENT was able to interest schools outside the consortium, as for the case of AIRSAFE project in Italy, and with Volens Association in Romania that will support GreenSCENT in 6 other schools in rural areas of Romania the 2nd reporting period for developing a pilot activity about biodiversity using GreenSCENT competence framework and research protocol (questionnaire).	Also here we fully agree with the comments from M18. In particular, the participation of schools has been a success owing to the important role of the teachers, who happen to know pupils personally, to speak in addition to English, also the local language and, last but not least, to know how to engage. It has to be seen how engagement with participants from HEIs will materialize since the experiences so far in the project are, according to plan, more reduced (than with pupils). The method of "minor incentives" (Section 5.5) seems to work as well.

Table 2. Unforeseen risks for WP5, applied mitigation measures, comments about state at M18 from PTR and comments about state at M22 from WP5.

Risk Number	Description	Applied mitigation measures	Comments (M18)	Comments from WP5 (M22)
U1	Complexity of the assessment questionnaire may impact on participants and their responses (overload, drop-outs).	GreenSCENT Competence Questionnaire integrates several modules (biographical and socio-demographic section, brief implicit association testing, general knowledge and skills by GreenSCENT areas, pro-environmental behaviours, values, intentions, explicit attitudes). However, it is built in a modular way in order to adapt to the several audiences and activities in the project: items for primary school students and youth assemblies participants are different, module structure for Open Innovation Challenges participants was lighter) in order to reduce overload and avoid drop-outs.	Risk did not materialize.	Also by M22, that risk has not materialized. The applied measures seem to have worked.
U4	The potential lack of engagement from participants and occurrence of drop-outs could adversely impact the pilots success.	Addressing this risk requires proactive measures to maintain motivation, effective communication. GreenSCENT recruitment strategy will be set up in order to attract and motivate participants. Partners involved in the pilots (both demonstrators and pilots) have extensive experiences in implementation and communication and are fully committed to the objective. Well defined Gantt chart with well-structured operational plan.	Risk did not materialize.	Also by M22, that risk has not materialized. The applied measures seem to have worked.

10. Demonstrators

For a description of the contents and initial implementations of the demonstrator activities, see the report of the operational plan (D5.2) under the same section number as here in D5.3.

- 10.1 Environmental Monitoring App (ENG)
- 10.2 Citizen Journalism/Greenverse (ENG)
- 10.3 Interactive Documentary/Greenverse (ENG)
- 10.4 Microplastic Citizen Science (UAB)
- 10.5 Open Innovation (AGO)
- 10.6 Climathon (CRA)
- 10.7 CleanAir@Schools (4S)
- 10.8 GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App (BSC)
- 10.9 Youth Design Assemblies (Democracy X)

11. Pilot Implementations

Notes:

(1) In various subsections, it is mentioned that an “activity is not carried out within the period between project start (1 January 2022) and project end (31 December 2024).” This is the state of knowledge at the time of submission of D5.3. It may be that changes occur towards the end of the project and that an activity is actually carried out between the submission date of D5.3 (31 October 2024) and the end of the project.

(2) UNINETTUNO decided to take a tool (Knowledge Graph) that it had developed within GreenSCENT and put it into a separate, new, experimental demonstrator activity; see Section 11.6.6.

11.1 Pilot Partner UAB (ES)

11.1.1 Demonstrator Activity *GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App*

This activity is not carried out within the period between project start (1 January 2022) and project end (31 December 2024).

Note: In D5.2 (Section 11.1.1, with the same title as here), UAB was erroneously listed as a pilot partner for this activity, as CRA has learned since the delivery date of D5.2 (29 December 2023). CRA, as the responsible author of D5.2, apologizes here for this oversight.

- 11.1.1.1 *Technology Relevance*
- 11.1.1.2 *Implementation Statistics*
- 11.1.1.3 *Ethical Questions*
- 11.1.1.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*
- 11.1.1.5 *User Experience*
- 11.1.1.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

11.1.2 Demonstrator Activity *Youth Design Assemblies*

- 11.1.2.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: medium.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) Wi-Fi connection;
- (2) laptops or PCs;
- (3) mobile phones;
- (4) screen and projector.

All these technologies and appliances are regularly used by almost all young people in Europe.

11.1.2.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M10–M25.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 15 days.

The number of participants was: 56.

Note: UAB implemented the YDAs in four groups, each in a different city (Barcelona, Copenhagen, Novi Sad and Rome); the numbers shown above are the totals of these activities.

11.1.2.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.1.2.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24).

The specific risks identified for this activity concerned the safety of the YDA participants in each of the four cities (Section 11.1.2.2). This risk was mitigated by adult supervision during outdoor activities in the city.

11.1.2.5 *User Experience*

Each of the four YDAs met a total of seven times for seven different workshops, six of which were conducted online, while the sixth one was held in the four European cities (Section 11.1.2.2). The participating young people, aged between 14 and 25, were given the opportunity to influence the design and implementation of the various technologies and frameworks developed within the GreenSCENT project.

For example, during the workshops, participants co-created ideas on how to use the developed applications in educational settings and helped to design the resulting prototypes. A later workshop then followed up on how these ideas were taken up by the project partners, leading one participant to state that “*seeing the results [red: the implementation of the co-created insights] made me feel that I had contributed to the start of a greener Europe.*” The structure of seven workshops thus allowed participants to gain a sense of empowerment by experiencing that their voices were actually heard throughout the activity.

The addition of a physical workshop to complement the online workshops ensured even more community building than was possible through the online versions alone. Here, the participating young people manifested a sense of contributing to the green transition with their peers, consolidating the emerging interests that led them to participate in the pilot activity in the first place.

From the statements made by participants in the final workshop, it is clear that the YDAs have motivated many participants to take part in the green transition. The YDAs thus achieved their goal of being a catalyst for action.

11.1.2.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

This demonstrator activity acted as an important meeting point for young people from different partner countries, allowing them to share different cultural perspectives. It also fostered the sense of community that comes from working with like-minded people to create a more sustainable future.

11.2 Pilot Partner EA (GR)

11.2.1 *Demonstrator Activity Environmental Monitoring App*

This activity has not been carried out within the period between project start (1 January 2022) and the submission of D5.3. We describe here only the technology relevance.

11.2.1.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The Environmental Monitoring App required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) NoSQL oriented to document database management (MongoDB);
- (2) web application programming (Javascript, NodeJS);
- (3) cloud infrastructure design and management.

Some of these skills are state of the art in IT.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) Smartphone/tablet iOS or Android with OS version still supported by the manufacturer;
- (2) a fast Internet connection of at least 30 Mbps.

11.2.1.2 *Implementation Statistics*

11.2.1.3 *Ethical Questions*

11.2.1.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

11.2.1.5 *User Experience*

11.2.1.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

11.2.2 Demonstrator Activity *Citizen Journalism/Greenverse*

This activity has not been carried out within the period between project start (1 January 2022) and the submission of D5.3. We describe here only the technology relevance.

11.2.2.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The Citizen Journalism/Greenverse tool required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) NoSQL oriented to documents database management (MongoDB);
- (2) web programming (Javascript, React framework, NodeJS);
- (3) cloud infrastructure design and management.

Some of these skills are state of the art in IT.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) Desktop or laptop PC with modern browser (a recent version of Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, or others that support the HTML 5 standard and WebGL);
- (2) a fast Internet connection of at least 30 Mbps.

11.2.2.2 *Implementation Statistics*

11.2.2.3 *Ethical Questions*

11.2.2.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

11.2.2.5 *User Experience*

11.2.2.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

11.2.3 Demonstrator Activity *Interactive Documentary/Greenverse*

11.2.3.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The Interactive Documentaries/Greenverse tool required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) NoSQL oriented to documents database management (MongoDB);
- (2) web programming (Javascript, React framework, NodeJS);
- (3) cloud infrastructure design and management.

Some of these skills are state of the art IT.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) 360° cameras;
- (2) desktop/laptop PC with modern browser (a recent version of Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, or others that support the HTML 5 standard and WebGL);
- (3) smartphone/tablet iOS or Android with OS version still supported by the manufacturer;
- (4) a fast Internet connection of at least 30 Mbps.

With the exception of the 360° camera, the other equipment or services are easily available. However, 360° cameras are also becoming increasingly popular among young people.

11.2.3.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M28.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 8 weeks.

The number of participants was: 12.

The participants were pupils from 7th grade (12 years old).

11.2.3.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.2.3.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.2.3.5 *User Experience*

The students were first introduced to the interactive documentary platform in their school year 7. The GreenSCENT journey was about to begin and they were amazed to be able to record specific data based on the research they had already done. The mapping of the school was innovative and the 3D presentation was unique. They formed groups, carried out research (specifically on how pupils could make use of the environment, how they could create green spaces in the school grounds or how they could dispose of waste and recycle as much as possible) and began to create the documentary. At this point they realized that the creation of the documentary was extremely difficult because the platform itself was not sufficiently user-friendly to them and most of the students were not able to complete the task.

We strongly believe that interactivity can improve learning outcomes by encouraging critical thinking and active learning. Viewers can experiment, make decisions and see the consequences of those decisions, which can lead to a deeper understanding of the subject. The educational value is undeniable as long as the tool is accessible to all.

11.2.3.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

The following sectors were involved in the implementation of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site:

- (1) researchers from UNINETTUNO (demonstrator),
- (2) teachers from EA (pilot),
- (3) secondary school students from EA (participants).

While the interactive documentary platform was used by 7th grade students in Greece, the lack of interaction between students from different countries resulted in a limited intercultural impact within this subunit. The potential of the platform to promote intercultural exchange and collaboration remained untapped at this point due to the lack of international interaction between students.

11.2.4 *Demonstrator Activity Microplastic Citizen Science*

This activity has not been carried out within the period between project start (1 January 2022) and the submission of D5.3. We describe here only the technology relevance.

11.2.4.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: low.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The microplastic citizen science activity required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) laptop/PC;
- (2) spreadsheet software (e.g. Microsoft Excel).

Both technologies have been commonplace in industry, education and homes for decades.

- 11.2.4.2 *Implementation Statistics*
- 11.2.4.3 *Ethical Questions*
- 11.2.4.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*
- 11.2.4.5 *User Experience*
- 11.2.4.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

11.2.5 *Demonstrator Activity Climathon*

11.2.5.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: medium.

The Climathon required the following technologies for its development as a course:

- (1) database management (Windows™, Grapher™, text-based);
- (2) Fortran programming (Intel™, gfortran);
- (3) graphic design (Indesign™).

All of these tools have existed in their basic form for years to decades.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The Climathon required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) visualization machines (beamer, screen) for showing the slides;
- (2) calculation machines (computers) for replicating the analyses.

All of these tools have existed in their basic form for decades.

11.2.5.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M22.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 3 days.

The number of participants was: 5.

Note: the implementation was performed jointly (online) at EA and RGSMART.

11.2.5.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.2.5.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.2.5.5 *User Experience*

As reported in D5.2 (Section 11 therein), the demonstrator activity aimed to increase participants' knowledge and capacity in the following areas:

- (1) climate,
- (2) climate data,
- (3) climate data analysis.

The users (i.e., the participants) responded to a questionnaire about their experience, that is, the extent to which the aims were achieved. A suitable measure of the success of the demonstrator activity can be obtained by comparing the relative frequencies for the two time points before and after the demonstrator activity.

Note: The entries in the following table have been obtained by combining the entries from the Climathon activity implemented at the secondary education institutions EA (Section 11.2.5) and RGSMART (Section 11.5.4).

Relative frequencies	Before	After
<i>Knowledge about climate</i>		
Limited	69%	
Moderate	23%	50%
Extensive	8%	50%
<i>Knowledge about climate data</i>		
Limited	79%	21%
Moderate	14%	21%
Extensive	7%	57%
<i>Knowledge about climate data analysis</i>		
Limited	79%	33%
Moderate	21%	42%
Extensive		25%

11.2.5.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

The following cultures or sectoral areas came together in the implementation of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site:

- (1) industry and SME Owner (CRA) (Demonstrator),
- (2) teacher (EA) (Pilot),
- (3) pupils at secondary education institution (Participants).

The objective figures (Section 11.2.5.5) show the success of the implementation. This is supported on a more subjective basis, as those responsible for the demonstrator and pilot activities (numbers (1) and (2) above), who shared their experiences after the event, felt that the participants were engaged and present until the end of the activity.

As regards the "other direction", the demonstrator and pilot activity leaders also confirmed that the implementation of the activity contributed to the training of the teachers and activity developers.

11.2.6 *Demonstrator Activity CleanAir@Schools*

11.2.6.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

CleanAir@Schools required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) Air quality sensors: Palmes diffusion tubes;
- (2) CleanAir@Schools web interface;
- (3) CleanAir@Schools mobile application.

The air quality sensors existed and have been used for measuring air quality for decades. The CleanAir@Schools web interface was developed during the project and the mobile application was improved and adapted to the educational sector during the project. Please note that the activity is open to a less technological demand replacing or supporting points (2) and (3) with paper-based maps and paper deployment sheets.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

CleanAir@Schools required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) visual equipment (computer, screen) to display the educational material;
- (2) computers to work on the mapping of the monitoring sites (web interface);
- (3) tablets or smartphones to collect metadata (mobile application).

All of these tools have existed in their basic form for many years or decades.

Figure 1. Results: Air quality in the city of Athens was sampled at 128 locations. The different sampling sites of the study include 81 background sites (parks and schoolyards) and 45 traffic sites on internal roads and roads crossing the city. In addition, measurements were taken at 2 points inside the classrooms of the educational centres studied. This variety of sites has contributed to a better understanding of air quality in the city of Athens. The results obtained show that nitrogen dioxide (NO_2) concentrations in the city of Athens range from 7 to $103 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, with an average of $22.3 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

11.2.6.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. The following questions arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

Environmental data collection activities involving students can raise a number of ethical issues that need to be considered and carefully assessed. These projects often highlight disparities in environmental quality and its impact on different communities. For example, the concentration of NO₂ can vary significantly between areas of different socio-economic status. Students from wealthier neighbourhoods could place data collection tubes in areas with lower NO₂ levels due to more green spaces and better environmental conditions, while students from poorer neighbourhoods could collect data in areas with higher NO₂ levels due to industrial activities and dense traffic. This scenario raises several ethical considerations that will be explored during the implementation and data analysis discussion between teachers and students.

11.2.6.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.2.6.5 *User Experience*

The survey analysis was carried out by 4S.

11.2.6.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

The following sectorial areas came together in the implementation of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site:

- (1) data analysts from 4S (demonstrator),
- (2) teachers from EA (pilot),
- (3) pupils at primary and secondary education institution EA (participants),
- (4) parents (participants).

The collaboration between students in Greece and data analysts at 4S in Spain demonstrates the power of global collaboration in tackling environmental challenges. By installing NO₂ monitors across Athens (Figure 1), these students have taken a proactive approach to monitoring air quality, an issue that transcends borders. Their initiative not only benefits their local community, but also contributes valuable data to a broader understanding of the dynamics of air pollution. The partnership with 4S further enriched this endeavour, demonstrating the synergy between local action and international expertise.

11.2.7 Demonstrator Activity *GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App*

This activity has been recently described in detail in a project report (D3.5); here we describe shortly the activity and its implementation at EA.

11.2.7.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The application required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) react framework
- (2) Babylon.js
- (3) Figma design software (for the prototype and testing phase).

The application prioritizes accessibility by using web technologies that allow for the app to be used in the web browser of most mobile devices, desktop computers and tablets, without the need to install any additional software. All that is required to access the application is an Internet connection. This platform-agnostic design ensures a consistent user experience. The development uses the renowned React framework for a high-performance interface, complemented by the Babylon.js software for immersive three-dimensional environments. In particular, Babylon.js enables an augmented reality (AR) experience on compatible smartphones (currently excluding Apple iOS), adding interactively to lessons 3, 7 and 8 (see D3.5 for details).

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: high.

11.2.7.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M28.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 8 weeks.

The number of participants was: 2 teachers and 150 students (5th grade) from elementary school.

11.2.7.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.2.7.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.2.7.5 *User Experience*

The main users of the application are students aged 10 to 11, with some younger students participating in the pilot, as well as their teachers (late primary, early secondary levels).

The user experience of the application was highly praised, with 94% of users rating their experience as positive. Students particularly enjoyed the interactive elements, with the AR maps in lessons 7 and 8 being the most engaging features. In addition, 88% of users found the app visually appealing, although some suggested including more images or animations. Importantly, 100% of the students surveyed felt that the app helped them better understand air quality concepts. These findings underline the effectiveness of the application in terms of both engagement and educational value.

Note: To protect student privacy, all data collected during the pilot testing phase is anonymized. This ensures that honest and unbiased feedback can be gathered without the need for individual consent forms. As data is collected throughout the year, the report will be continually updated with anonymized responses from all pilot sites, providing a comprehensive and evolving picture of the user experience. See also Section 11.2.7.3 and D5.2.

11.2.7.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

The pilot testing phase of the application fostered valuable collaboration between different stakeholders. These included representatives from educational institutions (school administrators and teachers), research partners (Barcelona Supercomputing Centre) and university support staff. Such a collaborative approach proved to be beneficial for all involved.

Positive results were evident at both objective and subjective levels, demonstrating the success of the implementation with the results of the anonymized survey. Qualitatively, stakeholder feedback (specific names and roles omitted) indicated a high level of engagement and participation from the student participants.

11.2.8 *Demonstrator Activity Youth Design Assemblies*

The YDA was implemented at EA only as an online activity. The full demonstrator activity (i.e., including the face-to-face component implemented at various places) is described at an EU-wide level in Section 11.8.3.

- 11.2.8.1 *Technology Relevance*
- 11.2.8.2 *Implementation Statistics*
- 11.2.8.3 *Ethical Questions*
- 11.2.8.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*
- 11.2.8.5 *User Experience*
- 11.2.8.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

11.3 Pilot Partner MAYK (FI)

11.3.1 Demonstrator Activity *Environmental Monitoring App*

11.3.1.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The Environmental Monitoring App required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) NoSQL oriented to document database management (MongoDB);
- (2) web application programming (Javascript, NodeJS);
- (3) cloud infrastructure design and management.

Some of these skills are state of the art in IT.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) Smartphone/tablet iOS or Android with OS version still supported by the manufacturer;
- (2) a fast Internet connection of at least 30 Mbps.

11.3.1.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M17.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 2 days.

The number of participants was: 16

thereof:

- | | | |
|-----|----------------------------------|----|
| (1) | teachers: | 2; |
| (2) | lower secondary school students: | 8; |
| (3) | upper secondary school students: | 6. |

11.3.1.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.3.1.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.3.1.5 *User Experience*

The feedback showed moderate interest. It was noted that many similar tools already exist in Finland. The topics covered by the Environmental Monitoring App are in line with what is already well integrated in the Finnish school curricula. Other considerations include avoiding redundancy, as similar resources are widely available. Test participants also highlighted the importance of equal access to high-quality, engaging content in Finnish language, especially in the form of short educational videos, which are currently in short supply.

Key challenges include difficulties in securing external funding and the abundance of similar resources. Feedback from the test group emphasised the importance of ensuring that the Environmental Monitoring App covers uniquely useful topics. Planning activities two to three months in advance and focusing on content that fills gaps in existing resources are key mitigation strategies.

The test participants found the Environmental Monitoring App functional but expressed a need for additional engaging content, especially short, high-quality videos in Finnish. While the software is easy to use, there is a clear gap in localized content compared to the abundance of English-language resources.

11.3.1.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

While the app has limited novelty in Finland due to existing resources, it has the potential to make a significant cross-cultural impact through participation in future international projects. Testing has shown that addressing underrepresented environmental issues and providing localised content will make the app more appealing in different cultural contexts.

11.3.2 Demonstrator Activity *CleanAir@Schools*

This activity is not carried out within the period between project start (1 January 2022) and project end (31 December 2024).

- 11.3.2.1 *Technology Relevance*
- 11.3.2.2 *Implementation Statistics*
- 11.3.2.3 *Ethical Questions*
- 11.3.2.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*
- 11.3.2.5 *User Experience*
- 11.3.2.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

11.3.3 Demonstrator Activity *GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App*

This activity is not carried out within the period between project start (1 January 2022) and project end (31 December 2024).

- 11.3.3.1 *Technology Relevance*
- 11.3.3.2 *Implementation Statistics*
- 11.3.3.3 *Ethical Questions*
- 11.3.3.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*
- 11.3.3.5 *User Experience*
- 11.3.3.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

11.4 Pilot Partner RST (RO)

11.4.1 Demonstrator Activity *Environmental Monitoring App*

- 11.4.1.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The Environmental Monitoring App required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) NoSQL oriented to document database management (MongoDB);
- (2) web application programming (Javascript, NodeJS);
- (3) cloud infrastructure design and management.

Some of these skills are state of the art in IT.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) Smartphone/tablet iOS or Android with OS version still supported by the manufacturer;
- (2) a fast Internet connection of at least 30 Mbps.

11.4.1.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M27–M28.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 30 days.

The number of participants was:

- | | | |
|-------|--------------------------|-----|
| (1) | Teachers: | 8, |
| (2) | students: | 58, |
| | thereof: | |
| (2.1) | year 9 (13 years old): | 22, |
| (2.2) | year 10R (14 years old): | 18, |
| (2.3) | year 10S (14 years old): | 18. |

11.4.1.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. The following questions arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

- (1) What is the result of reporting the risks I encounter or notice?
- (2) Will there be connections with local authorities?
- (3) Is it ethical to point out specific companies or other entities without letting them know?

11.4.1.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.4.1.5 *User Experience*

The Environmental Monitoring App is very user friendly and easy to use, intuitive for both students and teachers.

11.4.1.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

Raising awareness among students regarding the issues that we are facing in different areas and social communities, both within the same country and among other regions and countries.

11.4.2 *Demonstrator Activity Citizen Journalism/Greenverse*

11.4.2.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The Citizen Journalism/Greenverse tool required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) NoSQL oriented to documents database management (MongoDB);
- (2) web programming (Javascript, React framework, NodeJS);
- (3) cloud infrastructure design and management.

Some of these skills are state of the art in IT.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) Desktop or laptop PC with modern browser (a recent version of Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, or others that support the HTML 5 standard and WebGL);
- (2) a fast Internet connection of at least 30 Mbps.

11.4.2.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M27–M29.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 60 days.

The number of participants was:

- | | | |
|-------|--------------------------|-----|
| (1) | Teachers: | 8, |
| (2) | students: | 58, |
| | thereof: | |
| (2.1) | year 9 (13 years old): | 22, |
| (2.2) | year 10R (14 years old): | 18, |
| (2.3) | year 10S (14 years old): | 18. |

11.4.2.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. The following questions arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

- (1) What is the result of reporting the risks I encounter or notice?
- (2) Will there be connections with local authorities?
- (3) Is it ethical to point out specific companies or other entities without letting them know?

11.4.2.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.4.2.5 *User Experience*

The Citizen Journalism/Greenverse tool features are straightforward and user friendly. Both teachers, and students found it easy to use it.

11.4.2.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

Raising awareness among students regarding the issues that we are facing in different areas and social communities, both within the same country and among other regions and countries.

11.4.3 *Demonstrator Activity Interactive Documentary/Greenverse*

11.4.3.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The Interactive Documentaries/Greenverse tool required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) NoSQL oriented to documents database management (MongoDB);
- (2) web programming (Javascript, React framework, NodeJS);
- (3) cloud infrastructure design and management.

Some of these skills are state of the art IT.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) 360° cameras;
- (2) desktop/laptop PC with modern browser (a recent version of Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, or others that support the HTML 5 standard and WebGL);
- (3) smartphone/tablet iOS or Android with OS version still supported by the manufacturer;
- (4) a fast Internet connection of at least 30 Mbps.

With the exception of the 360° camera, the other equipment or services are easily available. However, 360° cameras are also becoming increasingly popular among young people.

11.4.3.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M27–M28.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 14 days.

The number of participants was:

- | | | |
|-------|------------------------|-----|
| (1) | Teachers: | 10, |
| (2) | students: | 77, |
| | thereof: | |
| (2.1) | year 3 (7 years old): | 22, |
| (2.2) | year 4 (8 years old): | 21, |
| (2.3) | year 5 (9 years old): | 17, |
| (2.4) | year 6 (10 years old): | 17. |

11.4.3.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.4.3.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.4.3.5 *User Experience*

The Interactive Documentaries/Greenverse tool was found to be challenging to navigate and lacked intuitive features for students. The activities had to be repeated on multiple occasions due to difficulties encountered by both participants and organizers in saving resources. Nevertheless, subsequent to the resolution of these initial issues, the tool demonstrated considerable potential as a pedagogical resource. The assistance

provided by ENG was highly beneficial, enabling our educators to gain a comprehensive understanding of the tool's functionality.

11.4.3.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

None.

11.4.4 *Demonstrator Activity CleanAir@Schools*

11.4.4.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

CleanAir@Schools required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) Air quality sensors: Palmes diffusion tubes;
- (2) CleanAir@Schools web interface;
- (3) CleanAir@Schools mobile application.

The air quality sensors existed and have been used for measuring air quality for decades. The CleanAir@Schools web interface was developed during the project and the mobile application was improved and adapted to the educational sector during the project. Please note that the activity is open to a less technological demand replacing or supporting points (2) and (3) with paper-based maps and paper deployment sheets.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

CleanAir@Schools required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) visual equipment (computer, screen) to display the educational material;
- (2) computers to work on the mapping of the monitoring sites (web interface);
- (3) tablets or smartphones to collect metadata (mobile application).

All of these tools have existed in their basic form for many years or decades.

11.4.4.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M29–M30.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 12 days.

The number of participants was:

- | | | |
|-------|------------------------|-----|
| (1) | Teachers: | 7, |
| (2) | students: | 52, |
| | thereof: | |
| (2.1) | year 5 (9 years old): | 17, |
| (2.2) | year 6 (10 years old): | 17, |
| (2.3) | year 7 (11 years old): | 18. |

11.4.4.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. The following questions arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

- (1) Driving to school versus not driving?
- (2) What can I do to reduce the negative impact that I have on the air quality?
- (3) What can I do to increase the positive impact that I have on the air quality and engage other on replicating it?

11.4.4.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.4.4.5 *User Experience*

The software is highly interactive, facilitating the children's transition from the classroom to the community. It enables them to make observations, develop data collection skills and create graphs.

It draws upon previously learned concepts about air quality and air pollutants, establishing cross-curricular links to geography, mathematics, science and English.

The process of changing the location of the dosimeters was straightforward and intuitive. However, the procedure for resolving any issues encountered was somewhat unclear. Fortunately, the 4S team was able to provide clear guidance on how to address these issues.

11.4.4.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

It is possible to interact with members of the local community, business owners and representatives of the local government.

Young people can be helped to understand that air quality varies depending on the topography of an area and the economic profile of the region, as well as being made aware of the impact of human activity.

11.4.5 Demonstrator Activity *GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App*

This activity has been recently described in detail in a project report (D3.5).

11.4.5.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: high.

The GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) React framework;
- (2) Babylon.js;
- (3) Figma (for the prototype and testing phase).

The application prioritizes accessibility by using web technologies that allow for the app to be used in the web browser of most mobile devices, desktop computers, and tablets, without the need to install any additional software. All that is required to access the application is an Internet connection. This platform-agnostic design ensures a consistent user experience. Development uses the renowned React framework for a high-performance interface, complemented by Babylon.js for immersive 3D environments. In particular, Babylon.js enables an AR experience on compatible smartphones (which currently excludes Apple iOS), thus enriching lessons 3, 7, and 8 with interactive elements.

All this from the development of the activity also has a strong impact on its implementation.

11.4.5.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M27–M28.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 14 days.

The number of participants was:

- | | | |
|-------|------------------------|-----|
| (1) | Teachers: | 9, |
| (2) | students: | 77, |
| | thereof: | |
| (2.1) | year 3 (7 years old): | 22, |
| (2.2) | year 4 (8 years old): | 21, |
| (2.3) | year 5 (9 years old): | 17, |
| (2.4) | year 6 (10 years old): | 17. |

11.4.5.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.4.5.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.4.5.5 *User Experience*

The app is easy to use and suitable for 8–9 year olds.

11.4.5.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

None.

11.4.6 *Demonstrator Activity Youth Design Assemblies*

11.4.6.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: medium.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) Wi-Fi connection;
- (2) laptops or PCs;
- (3) mobile phones;
- (4) screen and projector.

All these technologies and appliances are regularly used by almost all young people in Europe.

11.4.6.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M10–M25.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 3 days.

The number of participants was:

- | | | |
|-------|----------------------------|----|
| (1) | Teachers: | 2, |
| (2) | students: | 4, |
| | thereof: | |
| (2.1) | year 12 (16–17 year olds): | 4. |

11.4.6.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.4.6.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24).

The students were under age 18; some of the funding was used to send a supervising teacher with them.

11.4.6.5 *User Experience*

It was very easy for the children to participate; however, it was difficult to recruit them because there were many activities to do before. A number of five students dropped out along the way.

11.4.6.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

Children visited different countries, interacted with different nationalities and cultures.

11.5 Pilot Partner RGSMART (RS)

11.5.1 Demonstrator Activity *Environmental Monitoring App*

11.5.1.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The Environmental Monitoring App required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) NoSQL oriented to document database management (MongoDB);
- (2) web application programming (Javascript, NodeJS);
- (3) cloud infrastructure design and management.

Some of these skills are state of the art in IT.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) Smartphone/tablet iOS or Android with OS version still supported by the manufacturer;
- (2) a fast Internet connection of at least 30 Mbps.

11.5.1.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M27–M28.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 5 days.

The number of participants was:

- (1) Teachers: 2,
- (2) students: 3,
thereof:
 - (2.1) 16 years old: 1,
 - (2.2) 17 years old 1,
 - (2.3) 18 years old : 1.

11.5.1.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. The following questions arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

- (1) What happens if I report the hazards I see or become aware of?
- (2) Will there be connections with local authorities?
- (3) Is it ethical to point out specific companies or other entities without letting them know?

11.5.1.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.5.1.5 *User Experience*

For both teachers and students, the Environmental Monitoring App is incredibly intuitive, user-friendly and simple to use.

11.5.1.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

To make pupils aware of the problems that exist in different social groups and places, both in our own country and in other nations and regions.

11.5.2 *Demonstrator Activity Citizen Journalism/Greenverse*

11.5.2.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The Citizen Journalism/Greenverse tool required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) NoSQL oriented to documents database management (MongoDB);
- (2) web programming (Javascript, React framework, NodeJS);
- (3) cloud infrastructure design and management.

Some of these skills are state of the art in IT.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) Desktop or laptop PC with modern browser (a recent version of Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, or others that support the HTML 5 standard and WebGL);
- (2) a fast Internet connection of at least 30 Mbps.

11.5.2.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M1–M31.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 31 months.

The number of participants was:

- (1) Teachers: 25,
- (2) students: 200.

A total of 25 teachers and 200 students have participated in the project so far. This activity has been carried out since the beginning of the project and continues today. It refers to the monitoring of all issues and activities carried out by GreenSCENT, as well as other related issues related to ecology, pollution, recycling and possible solutions to pollution problems.

11.5.2.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

The parents of the participating children supported and agreed with the implementation of the activities. Pupils, members of the environmental section of RGSMART, who researched these issues further, found additional texts that we published on social networks and the school website, in addition to all the issues published on the GreenSCENT website.

11.5.2.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24).

There was a risk about the reliability of the content researched by the students, which was mitigated by the fact that RGSMART school officials carried out pre-publication checks.

11.5.2.5 *User Experience*

RGSMART officials have found that the most effective approach to learning is through research, as this is the method through which one can gain the most knowledge.

11.5.2.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

The students did not limit their research to the territorial borders of the country, on the contrary, they broadened their horizons to Europe and the whole world. The first research content we published was later used by GreenSCENT on its website.

11.5.3 *Demonstrator Activity Interactive Documentary/Greenverse*

11.5.3.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The Interactive Documentaries/Greenverse tool required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) NoSQL oriented to documents database management (MongoDB);
- (2) web programming (Javascript, React framework, NodeJS);
- (3) cloud infrastructure design and management.

Some of these skills are state of the art IT.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) 360° cameras;
- (2) desktop/laptop PC with modern browser (a recent version of Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, or others that support the HTML 5 standard and WebGL);
- (3) smartphone/tablet iOS or Android with OS version still supported by the manufacturer;
- (4) a fast Internet connection of at least 30 Mbps.

With the exception of the 360° camera, the other equipment or services are easily available. However, 360° cameras are also becoming increasingly popular among young people.

11.5.3.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M29.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 1 day.

The number of participants was:

- | | | |
|-----|-----------|-----|
| (1) | Teachers: | 2, |
| (2) | students: | 10. |

11.5.3.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.5.3.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.5.3.5 *User Experience*

Participants offered suggestions on how to improve user interaction, but it took some time for them to become familiar with the platform provided. In the end, the platform provided a satisfactory experience.

11.5.3.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

In the coming school year 2024/2025, as part of their education, our students will be able to use this application to compare the level of pollution in our region with other European countries.

11.5.4 *Demonstrator Activity Climathon*

11.5.4.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: medium.

The Climathon required the following technologies for its development as a course:

- (1) database management (Windows™, Grapher™, text-based);
- (2) Fortran programming (Intel™, gfortran);
- (3) graphic design (Indesign™).

All of these tools have existed in their basic form for years to decades.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The Climathon required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) visualization machines (beamer, screen) for showing the slides;
- (2) calculation machines (computers) for replicating the analyses.

All of these tools have existed in their basic form for decades.

11.5.4.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M22.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 3 days.

The number of participants was: 20.

Note: the implementation was performed jointly (online) at EA and RGSMART.

11.5.4.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.5.4.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.5.4.5 *User Experience*

As reported in D5.2 (Section 11 therein), the demonstrator activity aimed to increase participants' knowledge and capacity in the following areas:

- (1) climate,
- (2) climate data,
- (3) climate data analysis.

The users (i.e., the participants) responded to a questionnaire about their experience, that is, the extent to which the aims were achieved. A suitable measure of the success of the demonstrator activity can be obtained by comparing the relative frequencies for the two time points before and after the demonstrator activity.

Note: The entries in the following table have been obtained by combining the entries from the Climathon activity implemented at the secondary education institutions EA (Section 11.2.5) and RGSMART (Section 11.5.4).

Relative frequencies	Before	After
<i>Knowledge about climate</i>		
Limited	69%	
Moderate	23%	50%
Extensive	8%	50%
<i>Knowledge about climate data</i>		
Limited	79%	21%
Moderate	14%	21%
Extensive	7%	57%
<i>Knowledge about climate data analysis</i>		
Limited	79%	33%
Moderate	21%	42%
Extensive		25%

11.5.4.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

The following cultures or sectoral areas came together in the implementation of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site:

- (1) industry and SME Owner (CRA) (Demonstrator),
- (2) head of school (RGSMART), teacher (RGSMART), university support (UNSPMF) (Pilot),
- (3) pupils at secondary education institution (Participants).

The objective figures (Section 11.2.5.5) show the success of the implementation. This is supported on a more subjective basis, as those responsible for the demonstrator and pilot activities (numbers (1) and (2) above), who shared their experiences after the event, felt that the participants were engaged and present until the end of the activity.

A notable support to pilot partner RGSMART was the presence of University Professor Biljana Basarin (UNSPMF) during the pilot implementation, facilitated by the fact that both partner institutions are located in the same city (Novi Sad, Serbia).

As regards the “other direction”, the demonstrator and pilot activity leaders also confirmed that the implementation of the activity contributed to the training of the teachers and activity developers.

11.5.5 Demonstrator Activity *CleanAir@Schools*

Note: The CleanAir@Schools demonstrator activity has been implemented jointly at RGSMART and UNSPMF; it is described only for the latter implementation (Section 11.7.4).

- 11.5.5.1 *Technology Relevance*
- 11.5.5.2 *Implementation Statistics*
- 11.5.5.3 *Ethical Questions*
- 11.5.5.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*
- 11.5.5.5 *User Experience*
- 11.5.5.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

11.5.6 Demonstrator Activity *GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App*

- 11.5.6.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The application required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) react framework
- (2) Babylon.js
- (3) Figma design software (for the prototype and testing phase).

The application prioritizes accessibility by using web technologies that allow for the app to be used in the web browser of most mobile devices, desktop computers and tablets, without the need to install any additional software. All that is required to access the application is an Internet connection. This platform-agnostic design ensures a consistent user experience. The development uses the renowned React framework for a high-performance interface, complemented by the Babylon.js software for immersive three-dimensional environments. In particular, Babylon.js enables an AR experience on compatible smartphones (currently excluding Apple iOS), adding interactively to lessons 3, 7 and 8 (see D3.5 for details).

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: high.

11.5.6.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M27–M28.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 1 day.

The number of participants was: 243,

thereof:

- (1) teachers: 3;
- (2) students: 240.

11.5.6.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.5.6.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.5.6.5 *User Experience*

The main users of the application are students aged 15-18 and their teachers (high school).

The user experience of the application was highly praised, with 100% of users rating their experience as positive. Students particularly enjoyed the interactive elements, with the AR maps in lessons 7 and 8 being the most engaging features. In addition, 100% of users found the app visually appealing, although some suggested the inclusion of more images or animations. Importantly, 100% of the students surveyed felt that the app helped them to better understand air quality concepts. These findings underline the effectiveness of the application in terms of both engagement and educational value.

Note: To protect student privacy, all data collected during the pilot phase were anonymized. This ensures that honest and unbiased feedback can be gathered without the need for individual consent forms. As data is collected throughout the year, the report will be continually updated with anonymized responses from all pilot sites, providing a comprehensive and evolving picture of the user experience.

The results of the anonymous survey showed that the implementation was successful, as both objective and subjective results were clear. Stakeholder feedback, with individual names and responsibilities removed, revealed a high level of student participation and engagement, and user satisfaction is a top priority for the demonstrator team through ongoing development. All pilot sites provide feedback and all bug reports are carefully investigated and resolved. This iterative process ensures the usability of the application as a learning tool. The collaborative aspect of the pilot, involving a wide range of stakeholders, has been crucial in guiding the development and optimizing the positive impact of the app on air quality education.

11.5.6.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

The pilot phase of the application fostered beneficial collaboration between different parties. These included administrators and professors from the educational institutions, research partners from BSC and support staff from the university. All parties benefited from this collaborative approach.

11.5.7 *Demonstrator Activity Youth Design Assemblies*

11.5.7.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: medium.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) Wi-Fi connection;
- (2) laptops or PCs;
- (3) mobile phones;
- (4) screen and projector.

All these technologies and appliances are regularly used by almost all young people in Europe.

11.5.7.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M10–M25.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 3 days.

The number of participants was: 4.

Note: the implementation was performed jointly (online) at EA and RGSMART.

11.5.7.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.5.7.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24).

One challenge was that the students at our school RGSMART are aged between 14 and 19, and minors must be accompanied by an adult. The meeting in Paris took place at a time of great unrest in the city, making it difficult for parents to give permission for their children to take part in the competition. One student therefore stayed at home and entered the competition online.

11.5.7.5 *User Experience*

The trips to Rome, Barcelona and Paris, as well as the young people's visit to Novi Sad, provided an opportunity to get to know each other and share knowledge and experience. The winners in Paris presented their idea to the city authorities for education in Novi Sad. The idea was recognized as excellent and has been implemented through the installation of five recycling machines in the city.

11.5.7.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

The following cultures or sectoral areas came together in the implementation of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site in Novi Sad, Serbia.

- (1) Industry (demonstrator partner Democracy X);
- (2) Professors and students (pilot partner UNSPMF),
- (3) Principals, teachers and students (RGSMART);
- (4) teachers, students, partners and guardians (from primary school as "associated" pilot partner).

Students from RGSMART took part in the following YDAs: in Rome, Italy; Barcelona, Spain; Paris, France and Novi Sad, Serbia. Young people from ten European countries took part in each of these meetings. In Rome the main theme was "From Farm to Fork", in Barcelona "Clean Air" and in Paris the students of our school took part in the final of the Sustainable Food Challenge 2023 competition, where they won. The idea of that event was to connect citizens and the city through recycling. That the city would reward conscientious citizens who were willing to use the recycling machines with various city benefits. When young people from several European countries visited Novi Sad, they had the opportunity to visit the Novi Sad Institute of NS Seme, City Green and UNSPMF. Many useful lectures were held on this occasion.

See also Section 11.5.7.5.

11.6 Pilot Partner UNINETTUNO (IT)

11.6.1 *Demonstrator Activity Environmental Monitoring App*

Note that UNINETTUNO implemented jointly the three demonstrator activities Environmental Monitoring App (Section 11.6.1), Citizen Journalism/Greenverse (Section 11.6.2) and Interactive Documentary (Section 11.6.3). Due to this fact, and also due to the strong technological dependence between the demonstrator activity Environmental Monitoring App on the one hand, and the demonstrator activity Citizen Journalism/Greenverse on the other (see the introductory paragraph of Section 11), there is a considerable overlap among the content of the three mentioned sections.

11.6.1.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The Environmental Monitoring App required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) NoSQL oriented to document database management (MongoDB);
- (2) web application programming (Javascript, NodeJS);
- (3) cloud infrastructure design and management.

Some of these skills are state of the art in IT.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) Smartphone/tablet iOS or Android with OS version still supported by the manufacturer;
- (2) a fast Internet connection of at least 30 Mbps.

11.6.1.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M30.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 1 week.

The number of participants was: 9,

thereof:

- (1) professors: 2;
- (2) HEI students: 7.

Note: The implementation of the Environmental Monitoring App involved interdisciplinary groups of university students from UNINETTUNO during the university Spring School course. The activity spanned over 3 interactive lessons from 11 June 2024 to 18 June 2024. The group was composed of students from engineering, psychology and communication sciences.

The students conducted comprehensive documentary research, field data collection, focus group discussions and the generation of multiple evidence-based reports on traffic pollution in various regions of Italy using the mobile application. They worked independently.

11.6.1.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. The following questions arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

- (1) What is the result of reporting the risks I encounter or notice?
- (2) Will there be connections with local authorities?
- (3) Is it ethical to point out specific companies or other entities without letting them know?

11.6.1.4

Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.6.1.5

User Experience

The educational activities with the demonstrator were conducted within the UNINETTUNO Spring School, an integrative interdisciplinary University course focused on the Smart Mobility area, which involved experts, contents and students coming from the following university courses.

- (1) Master Degree in Cognitive Processes and Technologies:
Experience Design;
- (2) Bachelor Degree in Socio-Psychological Disciplines:
Psychotechnologies;
- (3) Bachelor Degree in Communication Sciences:
Digital Technologies and Cognitive Processes;
- (4) Master Degree in Management Engineering:
Industrial Plants, Production Scheduling and Control,
Geology, Tunnelling, Artificial Adaptive Systems;
- (5) Master Degree in Business Management and Digital Technologies:
Green Economy and Organisational Change.

The user experience of the Environmental Monitoring App was evaluated as follows:

- (1) **Engagement:** Students found the interactive nature of the project engaging and educational.
- (2) **Ease of Use:** The software was intuitive, allowing students to collect evidence of traffic congestion and air pollution in the real context.
- (3) **Learning Outcomes:** Students reported a better understanding of air pollution sources coming from urban mobility, along with improved digital and analytical skills.

In particular, the challenge of the implementation of the demonstrator activity was to investigate road congestion and air pollution.

The specific objectives of the implementation activities were as follows.

- (1) Recognize the concepts of complexity, urban energy self-sufficiency and smart building.
- (2) Plan to obtain information about services, traffic conditions, climate and the state of the air we breathe from data provided by users as well as from the entire smart infrastructure network.

- (3) Illustrate what road congestion is and what the goals of smart mobility are (e.g., safety, noise reduction; improving efficiency, the sharing culture; know what a sustainable urban mobility plan is; what is meant by a digital city).
- (4) Learn and understand the basics of air pollution, including signs, types, sources and their impacts on human health.
- (5) Become familiar with a scientifically based analysis approach, which includes documentation, analysis, measurement, evaluation and improvement.
- (6) Correlate data with the invisible phenomena of air pollution and connect air quality with various contextual influences, such as geographical location, urban traffic, industrial activity, waste management and other human activities.

The activity can be summarized in the following terms.

- (1) ex-ante GreenSCENT questionnaire;
- (2) each team will implement the following activities:
 - (2.1) select a source of air pollution in the real context,
 - (2.2) in-field data collection campaign,
 - (2.3) data analysis and interpretation,
 - (2.4) create a storyline for the presentation of the results,
 - (2.5) formulate the lesson learnt by communicating the results through an interactive documentary;
- (3) ex-post GreenSCENT questionnaire.

The participants comprised educators, facilitators, managers and students. The number of professors was 2. The number of students involved was 7: Bachelor's degree students enrolled in Engineering, Economics, Communication Sciences or Psychology. The entire activity was facilitated and supervised by the professors.

The activities took place online through interactive classes. The research investigation was carried out by the students in cities of Italy: Verona, Modena, Carpi, Mirandola, Livorno, Siena, Grosseto, Civitavecchia, Rome, Naples and Bari.

The project successfully integrated theoretical knowledge with practical application, enhancing the overall learning experience.

11.6.1.6

Cross-Cultural Impact

The UNINETTUNO professors introduced the demonstrator during the interactive classes of the Spring School course. Students welcomed the interdisciplinary, practical nature of the project that helped to contextualize much of the theoretical knowledge learned in class into tangible artefacts realized by means of the GreenSCENT demonstrators.

Due to the geographic diversity of the students, the educational activities guided by the Environmental Monitoring App raised awareness about smart transportation among them and their social communities in many different regional areas of Italy, providing the research with much evidence and resources of urban pollution along the Italian country. The demonstrator had a significant cross-cultural impact via the following.

- (1) **Collaborative Learning.** Promoting interdisciplinary and cross-cultural collaboration among students from different academic backgrounds.
- (2) **Global Relevance.** Addressing global issues of sustainable mobility and pollution, making the project relevant to diverse geographical and socio-economic contexts, especially for many Italian regions.
- (3) **Community Awareness.** Raising awareness about environmental issues within the students' families and local communities, fostering a culture of sustainability among various regions of Italy.

The Environmental Monitoring App demonstrated the potential of collaborative and interdisciplinary approaches in addressing complex global challenges.

11.6.2 Demonstrator Activity *Citizen Journalism/Greenverse*

11.6.2.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The Citizen Journalism/Greenverse tool required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) NoSQL oriented to documents database management (MongoDB);
- (2) web programming (Javascript, React framework, NodeJS);
- (3) cloud infrastructure design and management.

Some of these skills are state of the art in IT.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) Desktop or laptop PC with modern browser (a recent version of Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, or others that support the HTML 5 standard and WebGL);
- (2) a fast Internet connection of at least 30 Mbps.

11.6.2.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M30.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 1 week.

The number of participants was: 9,

thereof:

- (1) professors: 2;
- (2) HEI students: 7.

Note: The implementation of Citizen Journalism/Greenverse involved interdisciplinary groups of university students from UNINETTUNO during the university Spring School course. The activity spanned over 2 interactive lessons from 11 June 2024 to 18 June 2024. The group was composed of students from engineering, psychology and communication sciences.

The students conducted comprehensive documentary research, conducted fieldwork data collection, held focus group discussions and created multiple pieces of evidence related to traffic pollution in various regions of Italy using the Citizen Journalism/Greenverse approach. They worked individually.

11.6.2.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. The following questions arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

- (1) What is the result of reporting the risks I encounter or notice?
- (2) Will there be connections with local authorities?
- (3) Is it ethical to point out specific companies or other entities without letting them know?

11.6.2.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.6.2.5 *User Experience*

The educational activities with the demonstrator were conducted within the UNINETTUNO Spring School, an integrative interdisciplinary University course focused on the Smart Mobility area, which involved experts, contents and students coming from the following university courses.

- (1) Master Degree in Cognitive Processes and Technologies:
Experience Design;
- (2) Bachelor Degree in Socio-Psychological Disciplines:

Psychotechnologies;

- (3) Bachelor Degree in Communication Sciences:
Digital Technologies and Cognitive Processes;
- (4) Master Degree in Management Engineering:
Industrial Plants, Production Scheduling and Control,
Geology, Tunnelling, Artificial Adaptive Systems;
- (5) Master Degree in Business Management and Digital Technologies:
Green Economy and Organisational Change.

The user experience of Citizen Journalism/Greenverse was evaluated as follows:

- (1) **Engagement:** Students found the interactive nature of the project engaging and educational.
- (2) **Ease of Use:** The software was intuitive, allowing students to map and geolocalize the evidence of traffic congestion and air pollution along many regions of Italy.
- (3) **Learning Outcomes:** Students reported a better understanding of air pollution sources coming from urban mobility, along with improved digital and analytical skills.

In particular, the challenge of the implementation of the demonstrator activity was to investigate road congestion and air pollution.

The specific objectives of the implementation activities were as follows.

- (1) Recognize the concepts of complexity, urban energy self-sufficiency and smart building.
- (2) Plan to obtain information about services, traffic conditions, climate and the state of the air we breathe from data provided by users as well as from the entire smart infrastructure network.
- (3) Illustrate what road congestion is and what the goals of smart mobility are (e.g., safety, noise reduction; improving efficiency, the sharing culture; know what a sustainable urban mobility plan is; what is meant by a digital city).
- (4) Learn and understand the basics of air pollution, including signs, types, sources and their impacts on human health.
- (5) Become familiar with a scientifically based analysis approach, which includes documentation, analysis, measurement, evaluation and improvement.
- (6) Correlate data with the invisible phenomena of air pollution and connect air quality with various contextual influences, such as geographical location, urban traffic, industrial activity, waste management and other human activities.

The activity can be summarized in the following terms.

- (1) ex-ante GreenSCENT questionnaire;
- (2) each team will implement the following activities:
 - (2.1) select a source of air pollution in the real context,
 - (2.2) in-field data collection campaign,
 - (2.3) data analysis and interpretation,
 - (2.4) create a storyline for the presentation of the results,
 - (2.5) formulate the lesson learnt by communicating the results through an interactive documentary;
- (3) ex-post GreenSCENT questionnaire.

The participants comprised educators, facilitators, managers and students. The number of professors was 2. The number of students involved was 7: Bachelor's degree students enrolled in Engineering, Economics, Communication Sciences or Psychology. The entire activity was facilitated and supervised by the professors.

The activities took place online through interactive classes. The research investigation was carried out by the students in cities of Italy: Verona, Modena, Carpi, Mirandola, Livorno, Siena, Grosseto, Civitavecchia, Rome, Naples and Bari.

The project successfully integrated theoretical knowledge with practical application, enhancing the overall learning experience.

11.6.2.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

The UNINETTUNO professors introduced the demonstrator during the interactive classes of the Spring School course. Students welcomed the interdisciplinary, practical nature of the project that helped to contextualize much of the theoretical knowledge learned in class into tangible artefacts realized by means of the GreenSCENT demonstrators.

Due to the geographic diversity of the students, the educational activities guided by Citizen Journalism/Greenverse raised awareness about smart transportation among them and their social communities in many different regional areas of Italy, providing the research with much evidence and resources of urban pollution along the Italian country. The demonstrator had a significant cross-cultural impact via the following.

- (1) **Collaborative Learning.** Promoting interdisciplinary and cross-cultural collaboration among students from different academic backgrounds.
- (2) **Global Relevance.** Addressing global issues of sustainable mobility and pollution, making the project relevant to diverse geographical and socio-economic contexts, especially for many Italian regions.
- (3) **Community Awareness.** Raising awareness about environmental issues within the students' families and local communities, fostering a culture of sustainability among various regions of Italy.

Hence, Citizen Journalism/Greenverse demonstrated the potential of collaborative and interdisciplinary approaches in addressing complex global challenges.

11.6.3 Demonstrator Activity *Interactive Documentary/Greenverse*

11.6.3.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The Interactive Documentaries/Greenverse tool required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) NoSQL oriented to documents database management (MongoDB);
- (2) web programming (Javascript, React framework, NodeJS);
- (3) cloud infrastructure design and management.

Some of these skills are state of the art IT.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) 360° cameras;
- (2) desktop/laptop PC with modern browser (a recent version of Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, or others that support the HTML 5 standard and WebGL);
- (3) smartphone/tablet iOS or Android with OS version still supported by the manufacturer;
- (4) a fast Internet connection of at least 30 Mbps.

With the exception of the 360° camera, the other equipment or services are easily available. However, 360° cameras are also becoming increasingly popular among young people.

11.6.3.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M30.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 1 week.

The number of participants was: 6,

thereof:

- (1) professors: 2;
- (2) HEI students: 4.

Note: The implementation of the Interactive Documentary/Greenverse demonstrator involved interdisciplinary groups of university students from UNINETTUNO during the university Spring School course. The activity spanned over 1 interactive lesson from 11 June 2024 to 18 June 2024. The group was composed of students from engineering, psychology and communication sciences.

The students conducted comprehensive documentary research, conducted fieldwork data collection, held focus group discussions and created multiple pieces of evidence related to traffic pollution in various regions of Italy using the technology. They worked individually.

11.6.3.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. The following questions arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

- (1) What is the result of reporting the risks I encounter or notice?
- (2) Will there be connections with local authorities?
- (3) Is it ethical to point out specific companies or other entities without letting them know?

11.6.3.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.6.3.5 *User Experience*

The educational activities with the demonstrator were conducted within the UNINETTUNO Spring School, an integrative interdisciplinary University course focused on the Smart Mobility area, which involved experts, contents and students coming from the following university courses.

- (1) Master Degree in Cognitive Processes and Technologies:
Experience Design;
- (2) Bachelor Degree in Socio-Psychological Disciplines:
Psychotechnologies;
- (3) Bachelor Degree in Communication Sciences:
Digital Technologies and Cognitive Processes;
- (4) Master Degree in Management Engineering:

- Industrial Plants, Production Scheduling and Control,
Geology, Tunnelling, Artificial Adaptive Systems;
- (5) Master Degree in Business Management and Digital Technologies:
Green Economy and Organisational Change.

The user experience of the Interactive Documentary/Greenverse demonstrator was evaluated as follows:

- (1) **Engagement:** Students found the interactive nature of the project engaging and educational.
- (2) **Ease of Use:** Not all the students found Greenverse component easy to use but, owing to a dedicated training session provided by the UNINETTUNO professors, they were able to understand and use the software independently at home without any particular issue.
- (3) **Learning Outcomes:** Students reported a better understanding of air pollution sources coming from urban mobility, along with improved digital and analytical skills.

In particular, the challenge of the implementation of the demonstrator activity was to investigate road congestion and air pollution.

The specific objectives of the implementation activities were as follows.

- (1) Recognize the concepts of complexity, urban energy self-sufficiency and smart building.
- (2) Plan to obtain information about services, traffic conditions, climate and the state of the air we breathe from data provided by users as well as from the entire smart infrastructure network.
- (3) Illustrate what road congestion is and what the goals of smart mobility are (e.g., safety, noise reduction; improving efficiency, the sharing culture; know what a sustainable urban mobility plan is; what is meant by a digital city).
- (4) Learn and understand the basics of air pollution, including signs, types, sources and their impacts on human health.
- (5) Become familiar with a scientifically based analysis approach, which includes documentation, analysis, measurement, evaluation and improvement.
- (6) Correlate data with the invisible phenomena of air pollution and connect air quality with various contextual influences, such as geographical location, urban traffic, industrial activity, waste management and other human activities.

The activity can be summarized in the following terms.

- (1) ex-ante GreenSCENT questionnaire;
- (2) each team will implement the following activities:
 - (2.1) select a source of air pollution in the real context,

- (2.2) in-field data collection campaign,
 - (2.3) data analysis and interpretation,
 - (2.4) create a storyline for the presentation of the results,
 - (2.5) formulate the lesson learnt by communicating the results through an interactive documentary;
- (3) ex-post GreenSCENT questionnaire.

The participants comprised educators, facilitators, managers and students. The number of professors was 2. The number of students involved was 4: Bachelor's degree students enrolled in Engineering, Economics, Communication Sciences or Psychology. The entire activity was facilitated and supervised by the professors.

The activities took place online through interactive classes. The research investigation was carried out by the students in cities of Italy: Verona, Modena, Carpi, Mirandola, Livorno and Civitavecchia.

The project successfully integrated theoretical knowledge with practical application, enhancing the overall learning experience.

11.6.3.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

The UNINETTUNO professors introduced the demonstrator during the interactive classes of the Spring School course. Students welcomed the interdisciplinary, practical nature of the project that helped to contextualize much of the theoretical knowledge learned in class into tangible artefacts realized by means of the GreenSCENT demonstrators.

Due to the geographic diversity of the students, the educational activities guided by Greenverse raised awareness about smart transportation among them and their social communities in many different regional areas of Italy, providing the research with much evidence and resources of urban pollution along the Italian country. The demonstrator had a significant cross-cultural impact via the following.

- (1) **Collaborative Learning.** Promoting interdisciplinary and cross-cultural collaboration among students from different academic backgrounds.
- (2) **Global Relevance.** Addressing global issues of sustainable mobility and pollution, making the project relevant to diverse geographical and socio-economic contexts, especially for many Italian regions.
- (3) **Community Awareness.** Raising awareness about environmental issues within the students' families and local communities, fostering a culture of sustainability among various regions of Italy.

The activities carried out for Interactive Documentary/Greenverse demonstrated the potential of collaborative and interdisciplinary approaches in addressing complex global challenges.

11.6.4 *Demonstrator Activity Climathon*

This activity is not carried out within the period between project start (1 January 2022) and project end (31 December 2024).

11.6.4.1	<i>Technology Relevance</i>
11.6.4.2	<i>Implementation Statistics</i>
11.6.4.3	<i>Ethical Questions</i>
11.6.4.4	<i>Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update</i>
11.6.4.5	<i>User Experience</i>
11.6.4.6	<i>Cross-Cultural Impact</i>

11.6.5 Demonstrator Activity *CleanAir@Schools*

Preliminary note: UNINETTUNO implemented the CleanAir@Schools activity in two different locations. While the technology is the same for both (Section 11.6.5.1), the implementation was very different. Therefore, the first implementation, at the Istituto Comprensivo Largo Cocconi Primary School, Rome, Italy, is described in Sections 11.6.5.2 to 11.6.5.6, while the second implementation, at the rural schools in Dâmbovița County, Romania, is described in Sections 11.6.5.7 to 11.6.5.11.

11.6.5.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

CleanAir@Schools required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) Air quality sensors: Palmes diffusion tubes;
- (2) CleanAir@Schools web interface;
- (3) CleanAir@Schools mobile application.

The air quality sensors existed and have been used for measuring air quality for decades. The CleanAir@Schools web interface was developed during the project and the mobile application was improved and adapted to the educational sector during the project. Please note that the activity is open to a less technological demand replacing or supporting points (2) and (3) with paper-based maps and paper deployment sheets.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

CleanAir@Schools required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) visual equipment (computer, screen) to display the educational material;
- (2) computers to work on the mapping of the monitoring sites (web interface);
- (3) tablets or smartphones to collect metadata (mobile application).

All of these tools have existed in their basic form for many years or decades.

11.6.5.2 *Italy Implementation: Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M26–M30.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 16 weeks.

The number of participants was: 81,

thereof:

- | | | |
|-----|---------------------|-----|
| (1) | first-year pupils: | 14; |
| (2) | second-year pupils: | 17; |
| (3) | third-year pupils: | 22; |
| (4) | fourth-year pupils: | 20; |
| (5) | educators: | 8. |

Note: The demonstration activity was carried out at the Largo Cocconi Educational Institution in Rome, Italy. The activities involved 4 classes of primary school students aged between 6 and 11 years (two in 3rd grade and two in 5th grade) to map the air quality of the surrounding areas of the Cocconi institution. The duration of the CleanAir@School demonstration activity at the pilot site was from 19 February 2024 to 6 June 2024. The implementation was supervised by UNINETTUNO, carried out locally by the Cocconi Institution and the results collected were analysed by 4S.

11.6.5.3 *Italy Implementation: Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. The following questions arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

Environmental data collection activities involving students can raise a number of ethical issues that need to be considered and carefully assessed. These projects often highlight disparities in environmental quality and its impact on different communities. For example, the concentration of NO₂ can vary significantly between areas of different socio-economic status. Students from wealthier neighbourhoods could place data collection tubes in areas with lower levels of NO₂ due to more green spaces and better environmental conditions, while students from poorer neighbourhoods could collect data in areas with higher levels of NO₂ due to pollution from anthropogenic activities. This scenario raises several ethical considerations that are explored during the implementation and data analysis discussion between educators and pupils.

11.6.5.4 *Italy Implementation: Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24).

The following possible risks foreseen in the planning occurred:

- (1) poor understanding of how the measurement process works due to its novelty for all teachers involved;
- (2) lack of technical knowledge on the part of teachers.

The following mitigation measures were implemented:

- (1) translation of all teaching materials, presentations and learning units into Italian;
- (2) organizing a preliminary online briefing (seminar) with the teachers to check the necessary equipment (tubes, hardware and software) and to organize the planning activities for the main phases (choice of sites, placement and collection of the tubes);
- (3) supplying technical support for the use of the digital tools of the CleanAir@Schools demonstrator.

11.6.5.5

Italy Implementation: User Experience

The **objectives** of the activity were:

- (1) to learn and understand the basics of air pollution such as characteristics, types, sources and effects on human health;
- (2) to become familiar with a scientifically based approach to analysis, including documentation, analysis, measurement, evaluation and improvement;
- (3) to become able to correlate data with the invisible phenomena of air pollution and relate air quality to multiple contextual influences such as geographical location, urban traffic, industrial activity, waste management and other human activities.

A note on the **participants** (teachers, facilitators, managers, students): Eight teachers were involved in the activity. They integrated CleanAir@Schools into their lessons, which include subjects such as geography, science and biology. The activities were carried out in two third-grade classes and two fifth-grade classes of the Cocconi Primary School. The whole activity was supervised by the teachers.

The activity took place in the Centocelle district of the city of Rome, Italy, in following **phases**.

- (1) 19 February 2024: GreenSCENT training and presentation of the CleanAir@Schools demonstrator;
- (2) 4 March 2024: Online briefing with teachers
- (3) 4 March 2024: Access to digital resources and guidelines granted to teachers;
- (4) 5 to 8 March 2024: placement of the tubes;
- (5) 8 March to 15 April 2024: regular checks on the status of the dosimeters;
- (6) 15 to 19 April 2024: collection of the tubes;

(7) 31 May 2024: submission of the report.

A note on the data collected, analysis and interpretation: The citizen science project with the educational institution in the district of Rome has provided more detailed information on local air quality. It has also contributed to a better understanding of environmental issues related to air pollution around the Cocconi Institution. Air quality sampling in Rome was carried out at 76 locations, including:

- (1) an indoor point in a classroom near the main roads;
- (2) an outdoor point in the main playground;
- (3) a point at the main entrance of the school;
- (4) points from sources away from traffic;
- (5) points near busy roads.

This variety of points has helped to improve the understanding of air quality in Rome (Figure 2). The results obtained show that NO₂ concentrations in the vicinity of Cocconi range from 11 to 44 µg/m³, with an average of 28 µg/m³.

Figure 2. Results: Air quality in the city of Rome. See the text for details.

Lessons learned. The practical activity offered by the CleanAir@Schools demonstrator (placing and collecting the tubes) was an ideal pretext to get students interested in the learning units offered at GreenSCENT. The digital technologies provided (GreenSCENT and CleanAir@Schools Apps) were of great interest to the students.

Participation and engagement. The activities were important to give students a multidisciplinary perspective. Pupils learned to ask the right questions so that their answers would contribute to a better relationship with nature. Inquiry as a pedagogical practice promotes an exploratory learning process. The search for answers to these questions involves a variety of processes and ways of thinking that support the development of new scientific knowledge.

Familiarity with the process of scientific inquiry facilitated students' own acquisition of scientific knowledge and an understanding of how scientific knowledge develops.

The project method had a significant impact on the attitude and behaviour of the students involved in the CleanAir@Schools activity. The learning strategies promoted transformative learning and collaborative activities based on encouraging cooperation and developing social inclusion skills.

11.6.5.6 *Italy Implementation: Cross-Cultural Impact*

The GreenSCENT team took the CleanAir@Schools demonstrator to a public school in Rome, Italy. Students welcomed the interdisciplinary, hands-on nature of the project, which helped to contextualize much of the theoretical knowledge learned in the classroom.

The implementation of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site brought together the following sectors:

- (1) data analysts from 4S (i.e., the developer of the CleanAir@Schools demonstrator);
- (2) teachers from the Largo Cocconi Institution (local pilot site representatives);
- (3) pupils of the primary school of the Cocconi Institution (participants);
- (4) parents of the pupils (participants);
- (5) researchers from UNINETTUNO (supervisors).

The collaboration between students and teachers in Italy and data analysts at in Spain demonstrates the power of global cooperation in tackling environmental challenges. By installing NO₂ monitors in the Centocelle district of Rome, these students have taken a proactive approach to monitoring air quality, an issue that transcends borders. Their initiative not only benefits their families and their local community, but also contributes valuable data to a broader understanding of the dynamics of air pollution in the entire Cocconi area. The partnership with UNINETTUNO and 4S has enriched this effort, demonstrating the synergy between local action and international expertise.

11.6.5.7 *Romania Implementation: Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M27–M28.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 7 weeks.

The number of participants was: ~180.

Note: The demonstration activity took place in Dâmbovița County, Romania, in two cities (Fieni and Pucioasa) and in two rural communities (Lucieni and Moroeni). A total of five schools (one high school and four secondary schools) mapped the air quality of the surrounding areas. The duration of the demonstration activity at the pilot site was from 4 March to 19 April 2024. The number of participants was: about 180; per school, about 25 to 40 students and 2 to 3 teachers participated.

The implementation was carried out within a larger project called “The Living Treasures Near Us”, which is coordinated by the Volens Association in Dâmbovița County, Romania. The project also implemented the GreenSCENT Competence Framework in the mentioned schools. The aim was to encourage and guide children and young people to know, protect and promote elements of local biodiversity. Measuring air quality using the CleanAir@Schools tools was an optional component, but every single school chose to take part in this challenge.

11.6.5.8

Romania Implementation: Ethical Questions

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. The following questions arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

Environmental data collection activities involving students can raise a number of ethical issues that need to be considered and carefully assessed. These projects often highlight disparities in environmental quality and its impact on different communities. For example, the concentration of NO₂ can vary significantly between areas of different socio-economic status. Students from wealthier neighbourhoods could place data collection tubes in areas with lower levels of NO₂ due to more green spaces and better environmental conditions, while students from poorer neighbourhoods could collect data in areas with higher levels of NO₂ due to pollution from anthropogenic activities. This scenario raises several ethical considerations that are explored during the implementation and data analysis discussion between educators and pupils.

The context was also challenging, but this ultimately proved to be a strength of the project. The main supporter of the current implementation was Heidelberg Materials AG, a multinational company in the building materials industry. They have a concrete plant in Fieni, and they have often been accused (without scientific evidence) of being the main polluter in the area. However, confident in the improvements and investments they have made to move towards a more sustainable and environmentally friendly way of operating, they have agreed to support the implementation of the CleanAir@Schools activity in the respective schools. Both parties, the project initiators and the sponsor, took a leap of faith in continuing the activity.

11.6.5.9

Romania Implementation: Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24).

The following possible risks foreseen in the planning occurred:

- (1) poor understanding of how the measurement process works due to its novelty for all teachers involved;
- (2) The findings may have contributed to the emergence of tensions between the company/sponsor and the communities.

The following mitigation measures were implemented:

- (1) translation of all teaching materials, presentations and learning units into Italian;
- (2) organizing a preliminary online briefing (seminar) with the teachers to check the necessary equipment (tubes, hardware and software) and to organize the planning activities for the main phases (choice of sites, placement and collection of the tubes);
- (3) establishing a direct communication mode between the batch plant managers and the school teams implementing the CleanAir@Schools demonstrator: guided tours of the plant, debates and discussions with the technical director, exploration of potential sources of pollution and actions taken to transition to a sustainable mode of operation.

11.6.5.10

Romania Implementation: User Experience

The **objectives** of the activity were:

- (1) to learn and understand the basics of air pollution such as characteristics, types, sources and effects on human health;
- (2) to become familiar with a scientifically based approach to analysis, including documentation, analysis, measurement, evaluation and improvement;
- (3) to become able to correlate data with the invisible phenomena of air pollution and relate air quality to multiple contextual influences such as geographical location, urban traffic, industrial activity, waste management and other human activities.

A note on the **participants** (teachers, facilitators, managers, pupils): Three teachers/schools were involved. They teach different subjects (including but not limited to geography and biology). In Lucieni and Pucioasa, the project was adapted for primary school pupils by primary school teachers. In each school the project was closely supervised by the headmaster.

In the **follow-up interviews**, most of the teachers said that this was the first non-formal project that mobilized the whole school, from the management to the teachers, administrators, parents and students. The CleanAir@Schools demonstrator and the whole GreenSCENT project represented a real milestone in the extracurricular portfolio of these institutions.

The activity took place in Dâmbovița County (South), Romania, in two cities and two villages, in following **phases**.

- (1) 10 November 2023: GreenSCENT training and presentation of the CleanAir@Schools demonstrator;
- (2) 23 January 2024: deadline for the expression of interest from schools;
- (3) 22 February 2024: access to digital resources and guidelines granted to teachers;
- (4) 27 February 2024: online briefing with the Volens Association and the teachers;
- (5) 4 to 19 March 2024: installation of the tubes;
- (6) for four weeks: regular checks on the status of the dosimeters;
- (7) 4 to 19 April 2024: collection of the tubes;
- (8) 31 May 2024: submission of the report.

A note on the data collected, analysis and interpretation: The CleanAir@School citizen science project has contributed to improving students' knowledge about air pollution and its health effects. This was possible thanks to the implementation of an NO₂ measurement campaign using passive dosimeters, which allowed mapping the spatial distribution of NO₂ concentrations around five educational centres in Romania. The initiative was carried out within the framework of the GreenSCENT project. The passive dosimeters used are an indicative method and therefore the data obtained are indicative and cannot be used for regulatory compliance.

Air quality sampling in Romania was carried out at 93 sampling points. The different sampling sites in the study include 75 background sites (parks and schoolyards) and 15 traffic sites on internal roads and roads crossing the city. In addition, measurements were taken at 3 points inside the classrooms of the educational centres studied. This variety of sites has helped to improve the understanding of air quality in Romania. The results obtained indicate that NO₂ concentrations in Romania range from 4 to 24 µg/m³, with an average of 10.9 µg/m³.

The citizen science project, in cooperation with educational centres in Romania, has provided more detailed information on local air quality. It has also contributed to a better understanding of environmental issues related to air pollution around educational centres.

Lessons learned. The implementation of the CleanAir@Schools demonstrator was the first project of its kind for the participating schools in Romania. The practical activity (placing and collecting the tubes) was an ideal pretext to get students interested in the learning units offered by GreenSCENT. The digital technologies provided (GreenSCENT and CleanAir@Schools Apps) were of great interest to the students. Finally, here is an explanatory quote from one of the coordinating teachers:

The "Living Treasures Near Us" was a project that brought nature into the classroom and the students into nature, made them more enthusiastic about caring for it and combined traditional and new teaching methods.

Feedback. The following quote is from another teacher:

Students learned about air pollution from a multidisciplinary perspective, they found problems and proposed solutions. They learned to ask the right questions so that their answers would contribute to a better relationship with nature. Inquiry as a pedagogical practice promotes a question-led learning process. The search for answers to these questions involves a variety of processes and ways of thinking that support the development of new scientific knowledge.

Familiarity with the process of scientific inquiry facilitated the students' own acquisition of both scientific knowledge and an understanding of how scientific knowledge develops.

The project method had an outstanding impact on the attitudes and behaviour of the pupils involved in the activities. The research project method is one of those strategies that emphasize authenticity and the use of methods that are as close as possible to the children's world. It is also in line with the new trend of transforming the learning process into an individualized and participatory process, based on the promotion of cooperation and the development of social integration skills.

11.6.5.11

Romania Implementation: Cross-Cultural Impact

The Volens Association project, supported by the GreenSCENT team, introduced CleanAir@Schools to public schools in Romania. Moreover, the participating schools are located in small rural communities, where opportunities to participate in European and international projects are rare.

Students welcomed the interdisciplinary, hands-on nature of the project, which helped to contextualize much of the theoretical knowledge learned in class.

The implementation of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site brought together the following sectors:

- (1) data analysts from 4S (i.e., the developer of the CleanAir@Schools demonstrator);
- (2) teachers from Dâmbovița County (locally representing the pilot site);
- (3) high school and secondary school students from Dâmbovița County (participants);
- (4) parents and rural communities from the towns of Lucieni and Moroeni (participants).

The collaboration between students, teachers and rural communities in Romania and data analysts at 4S in Spain demonstrates the power of global collaboration in tackling environmental challenges. By installing NO₂ monitors in the Dâmbovița County region, these students have taken a proactive approach to monitoring air quality, an issue that transcends borders. Their initiative not only benefits their families and their local community, but also contributes valuable data to a broader understanding of the dynamics of air pollution in all selected Romanian areas. The partnership with 4S has further enriched this effort, demonstrating the synergy between local action and international expertise.

At the end of May 2024, the Volens Association conducted a series of interviews with representatives from each school (teachers and students), which were broadcast on the national radio station Radio Romania Cultural.

The interviewed people all said that the CleanAir@Schools activity had fostered cooperation between the school and the community in a way that exceeded their expectations. When asked about the most interesting experience of the whole project, the students invariably put CleanAir@Schools in the top 3.

The first trial of CleanAir@Schools had its hurdles, but its positive impact on the students and teachers is undeniable. Now that there is a better understanding of how the project works, it is envisaged to continue it in other schools in another region in Romania. The experience with this pilot project has shown that this is exactly the kind of challenge that Romanian public school students (especially those from rural areas) need in order to develop their skills for sustainable development. Here are links to some of the related content published by the association and the beneficiaries.

<https://www.patradereciclare.ro/greenscent-cadrul-european-de-competente-verzi-aplicat-pentru-prim-oara-in-scoli-publice-din-romania/>

[GreenSCENT - the European green competence framework applied for the first time in Romanian public schools]

<https://shorturl.at/dWccg>

[LinkedIn account of the Volens Association]

<https://shorturl.at/9RmPC>

[Facebook report page about GreenSCENT by the Aurel Rainu High School]

11.6.6 New, Experimental Demonstrator Activity *Knowledge Graph*

UNINETTUNO decided to take a tool (Knowledge Graph) that it had developed within GreenSCENT and embed it into a separate, new, experimental demonstrator activity. This tool has been applied in support of the YDAs and also within other WPs. It is described in D4.2 (GreenSCENT Training Kit for Teachers and Educators) and mentioned in D5.1 (Reports from Demonstrations and Workshops: Instructional Co-Design).

11.6.6.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The Knowledge Graph tool required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) Obsidian software (for the creation and management of interactive knowledge graphs);
- (2) data analysis tools (to collect and analyse data related to sustainable mobility and pollution);
- (3) digital collaboration tools (to enable students to communicate and collaborate during focus group discussions).

Some of these tools are state of the art IT.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) Digital collaboration tools: The technology enabled students to efficiently compile, visualize and connect complex data sets, fostering a comprehensive understanding of sustainable mobility and pollution issues.

11.6.6.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M29–M30.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 5 weeks.

The number of participants was: 16,

thereof:

- (1) students: 12;
- (2) professors: 4.

Note: Interdisciplinary groups of students from UNINETTUNO were involved in the implementation of the knowledge graph. The groups were composed of students from engineering, psychology and communication sciences. The project lasted for six interactive lessons from 21 May to 25 June 2024. The exploration of the

activity was executed in multidisciplinary teams, each comprising one engineering student, one psychology student and one economics student. That means a total of 12 students, divided into four groups of three members each. Each group was supervised by one professor. The students engaged in in-depth documentary research, data collection, focus group discussions and the creation of interactive knowledge graphs using Obsidian.

11.6.6.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. The following questions arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

- (1) **Bias in data collection:** Addressing potential biases that may arise from socio-economic disparities in the areas selected for study.

11.6.6.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24).

- (1) **Lack of participation.** This risk was mitigated by engaging students through interactive and gamified learning activities.
- (2) **Technical difficulties.** This risk was addressed by providing extensive training in the use of Obsidian and the other digital tools.
- (3) **Misinterpretation of data.** This risk was mitigated by regular supervision and guidance from educators to ensure accurate data analysis and presentation.

11.6.6.5 *User Experience*

The educational activities with the demonstrator were conducted within the UNINETTUNO Spring School, an integrative interdisciplinary University course focused on the Smart Mobility area, which involved experts, contents and students coming from the following university courses.

- (1) Master Degree in Cognitive Processes and Technologies:
Experience Design;
- (2) Bachelor Degree in Socio-Psychological Disciplines:
Psychotechnologies;
- (3) Bachelor Degree in Communication Sciences:
Digital Technologies and Cognitive Processes;

- (4) Master Degree in Management Engineering:
Industrial Plants, Production Scheduling and Control,
Geology, Tunnelling, Artificial Adaptive Systems;
- (5) Master Degree in Business Management and Digital Technologies:
Green Economy and Organisational Change.

The user experience of the Environmental Monitoring App was evaluated as follows:

- (1) **Engagement:** Students found the interactive nature of the project engaging and educational.
- (2) **Ease of Use:** The Obsidian software was intuitive, allowing students to create and manage knowledge graphs effectively.
- (3) **Learning Outcomes:** Students reported a better understanding of sustainable mobility and pollution, along with improved digital and analytical skills.

In particular, the challenge of the implementation of the demonstrator activity was to investigate road congestion and air pollution.

The specific objectives of the implementation activities were as follows.

- (1) Learn and understand the basics of air pollution, including signs, types, sources and their impacts on human health.
- (2) Become familiar with a scientifically based analysis approach, which includes documentation, analysis, measurement, evaluation and improvement.
- (3) Correlate data with the invisible phenomena of air pollution and connect air quality with various contextual influences, such as geographical location, urban traffic, industrial activity, waste management and other human activities.

The activity can be summarized in the following steps.

- (1) **ex-ante GreenSCENT questionnaire;**
- (2) **group formation:** each multidisciplinary team (1 engineering student, 1 psychology student, 1 communication student) carries out the following activities:
 - (2.1) data collection and analysis:
select a source of air pollution in the real context;
 - (2.2) in-field data collection campaign (traffic and mobility);
 - (2.3) data analysis and interpretation: correlations between congestion and pollution;
 - (2.4) definition of key concepts;
- (3) **group knowledge graph generation:**
 - (3.1) make direct links between the main concepts from Step (1);

- (3.2) build weak links (i.e. tags) by associating concepts based on observations and reasoning during the building phase;
- (3.3) explore and query the resulting knowledge graph:
- (4) **workshop on the finalisation of the knowledge graph:**
 - (4.1) as a knowledge artefact, the conceptual map is discussed and validated with the students;
 - (4.2) representatives from each group attend a workshop to merge individual graphs into a "super-graph";
 - (4.3) remove meaningless tags;
 - (4.4) merge overlapping tags;
 - (4.5) create new direct links by converting the most relevant associations;
 - (4.6) export the adjacency matrix;
 - (4.7) further evaluate the resulting graph;
- (5) **Lessons learned:**
 - (5.1) each representative will share the lessons learned within their original group, enhancing the collective understanding and application of smart mobility concepts;
 - (5.2) the lessons learned will be structured in a one-page specific format.
- (6) **ex-post GreenSCENT questionnaire.**

11.6.6.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

The Knowledge Graph activity had a significant cross-cultural impact through the following aspects:

- (1) **Collaborative learning:** Encouraging interdisciplinary and cross-cultural collaboration between students from different academic backgrounds.
- (2) **Global relevance:** Addressing global issues of sustainable mobility and pollution, making the project relevant to different geographical and socio-economic contexts.
- (3) **Community awareness:** Raising awareness of environmental issues within the students' local communities, fostering a culture of sustainability.

The activity demonstrated the potential of collaborative and interdisciplinary approaches to address complex global challenges.

The implementation of the Knowledge Graph demonstrator activity using Obsidian software at UNINETTUNO demonstrated the high relevance and effectiveness of integrating advanced technological tools in educational settings. By involving students in interdisciplinary groups, the project facilitated in-depth research, data collection and analysis on sustainable mobility and pollution. The students' ability to create

and manage interactive knowledge graphs greatly enhanced their understanding of complex environmental issues. The project addressed several ethical issues, ensuring responsible data handling and fair research practices, and successfully mitigated potential risks through proactive measures. The user experience was positive, with students reporting high levels of engagement and improved skills. The cross-cultural impact of the project was significant, promoting global awareness and collaboration between participants from different backgrounds. Overall, the Knowledge Graph demonstrator activity not only achieved its educational objectives, but also contributed valuable insights into sustainable mobility and pollution, highlighting the importance of interdisciplinary and collaborative approaches in tackling global challenges.

11.7 Pilot Partner UNSPMF (RS)

11.7.1 Demonstrator Activity *Interactive Documentary/Greenverse*

11.7.1.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The Interactive Documentaries/Greenverse tool required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) NoSQL oriented to documents database management (MongoDB);
- (2) web programming (Javascript, React framework, NodeJS);
- (3) cloud infrastructure design and management.

Some of these skills are state of the art IT.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) 360° cameras;
- (2) desktop/laptop PC with modern browser (a recent version of Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, or others that support the HTML 5 standard and WebGL);
- (3) smartphone/tablet iOS or Android with OS version still supported by the manufacturer;
- (4) a fast Internet connection of at least 30 Mbps.

With the exception of the 360° camera, the other equipment or services are easily available. However, 360° cameras are also becoming increasingly popular among young people.

11.7.1.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M29.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 1 day.

The number of participants was: 18 (8 teachers, 10 students).

11.7.1.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.7.1.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.7.1.5 *User Experience*

Participants needed time to get used to the provided platform, participants gave suggestions on how to improve user interaction. The final experience with the platform was satisfactory.

11.7.1.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

The following cultures or sectorial areas came together in the implementation of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site:

- (1) Industry (ENG, demonstrator partner);
- (2) HEI professors (UNINETTUNO, pilot facilitator);
- (3) professors and students (UNSPMF, pilot partner).

11.7.2 *Demonstrator Activity Microplastic Citizen Science*

This activity is not carried out within the period between project start (1 January 2022) and project end (31 December 2024).

11.7.2.1	<i>Technology Relevance</i>
11.7.2.2	<i>Implementation Statistics</i>
11.7.2.3	<i>Ethical Questions</i>
11.7.2.4	<i>Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update</i>
11.7.2.5	<i>User Experience</i>
11.7.2.6	<i>Cross-Cultural Impact</i>

11.7.3 Demonstrator Activity *Climathon*

11.7.3.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: medium.

The Climathon required the following technologies for its development as a course:

- (1) database management (Windows™, Grapher™, text-based);
- (2) Fortran programming (Intel™, gfortran);
- (3) graphic design (Indesign™).

All of these tools have existed in their basic form for years to decades.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The Climathon required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) visualization machines (beamer, screen) for showing the slides;
- (2) calculation machines (computers) for replicating the analyses.

All of these tools have existed in their basic form for decades.

11.7.3.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M27.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 2 days.

The number of participants was: 27.

11.7.3.3 Ethical Questions

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.7.3.4 Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.7.3.5 User Experience

As reported in D5.2 (Section 11 therein), the demonstrator activity aimed to increase participants' knowledge and capacity in the following areas:

- (1) climate,
- (2) climate data,
- (3) climate data analysis.

The users (i.e., the participants) responded to a questionnaire about their experience, that is, the extent to which the aims were achieved. A suitable measure of the success of the demonstrator activity can be obtained by comparing the relative frequencies for the two time points before and after the demonstrator activity.

Relative frequencies	Before	After
<i>Knowledge about climate</i>		
Limited	33%	22%
Moderate	44%	11%
Extensive	22%	67%
<i>Knowledge about climate data</i>		
Limited	78%	
Moderate	22%	56%
Extensive		44%
<i>Knowledge about climate data analysis</i>		
Limited	89%	
Moderate	11%	22%
Extensive		78%

11.7.3.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

The following cultures or sectoral areas came together in the implementation of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site:

- (1) industry and SME Owner (CRA) (Demonstrator),
- (2) teacher (EA) (Pilot),
- (3) students at higher education institution (Participants).

The objective figures (Section 11.7.3.5) show the success of the implementation. This is supported on a more subjective basis, as those responsible for the demonstrator and pilot activities (numbers (1) and (2) above), who shared their experiences after the event, felt that the participants were engaged and present until the end of the activity.

As regards the "other direction", the demonstrator and pilot activity leaders also confirmed that the implementation of the activity contributed to the training of the teachers and activity developers.

11.7.4 *Demonstrator Activity CleanAir@Schools*

11.7.4.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

CleanAir@Schools required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) Air quality sensors: Palmes diffusion tubes;
- (2) CleanAir@Schools web interface;
- (3) CleanAir@Schools mobile application.

The air quality sensors existed and have been used for measuring air quality for decades. The CleanAir@Schools web interface was developed during the project and the mobile application was improved and adapted to the educational sector during the project. Please note that the activity is open to a less technological demand replacing or supporting points (2) and (3) with paper-based maps and paper deployment sheets.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

CleanAir@Schools required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) visual equipment (computer, screen) to display the educational material;
- (2) computers to work on the mapping of the monitoring sites (web interface);
- (3) tablets or smartphones to collect metadata (mobile application).

All of these tools have existed in their basic form for many years or decades.

11.7.4.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M23.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 2 days.

The number of participants was:

(1)	HEI students:	10,
(2)	secondary school pupils	15,
(3)	secondary school pupils	28.

Note: the implementation of the demonstrator activity was performed jointly with RGSMART and elementary school Jovan Jovanovic Zmaj (Novi Sad, Serbia).

11.7.4.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.7.4.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24).

To ensure the consistency of the measurement data, it was essential to position the pipes at a precise height. This was also a crucial aspect in light of considerations pertaining to the safety and well-being of the participants. Furthermore, the possibility of pipes being stolen or destroyed, given their location in public spaces, is mitigated by this approach.

The prevailing meteorological conditions constituted an impediment to the installation of the sensors. The prevailing weather conditions were characterised by precipitation, which presented a potential risk of the ladder becoming unstable. The students were required to place the sensors at a height of 2.5 metres, which proved challenging in inclement weather. It may have been preferable to install them in the spring. No permission was sought from the city to install the sensors, which introduced the risk that they would be removed by the relevant authorities or by members of the public. The students who installed the sensors did so in their local area and visited the sites daily.

11.7.4.5 *User Experience*

Participants express a high level of engagement with the whole process of selecting sites, installing the tubes and later engagement in analysing the results.

Placing the sensor itself was interesting. It took a lot of teamwork to find the right location, place the sensor at the right height and then mark the location on the app. The plan was to mark the most common routes from home to school from the four corners of the city: The school is in the centre, so we listed the four most common routes. This made the students aware of the air pollution we inhale every day on our way to and from school. Many decided to come to school by bike or electric scooter.

11.7.4.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

RGSMART and Jovan Jovanovic Zmaj are schools that are very involved in environmental activities. We use social networks and share our knowledge, and we have presented all the results we have to the children in classes at school. We talked about the lack of recycling in our country. There are few companies in our country that use recycled materials. We compared this knowledge with countries in the region and Europe.

The following cultures or sectoral areas came together in the implementation of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site:

- (1) Industry (4S, demonstrator partner);
- (2) professors and students (UNSPMF, pilot partner),
- (3) head of school, teachers and pupils (RGSMART, pilot partner);
- (4) teachers, pupils, partners and legal guardians (elementary school as "associated" pilot partner).

11.7.5 *Demonstrator Activity Youth Design Assemblies*

11.7.5.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: medium.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) Wi-Fi connection;
- (2) laptops or PCs;
- (3) mobile phones;
- (4) screen and projector.

All these technologies and appliances are regularly used by almost all young people in Europe.

11.7.5.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M22.

There were four sites of pilot implementation at Novi Sad, Serbia:

- (1) UNSPMF,
- (2) Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops "Ns Seme",
- (3) Composting Site "Gradsko Zelenilo",
- (4) Hotel Veliki Conference Room.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 3 days.

The number of participants was: 23,

thereof:

- (1) students (from Denmark, Finland, Greece, Serbia and Spain): 12;
- (2) pupils (from Smart Grammar School, Novi Sad, Serbia): 5;
- (3) coordinator or demonstrator personnel (from Democracy X, EA and UNSPMF): 6.

11.7.5.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.7.5.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24).

The specific risks identified for this activity related to the safety of the YDA participants in the city of Novi Sad during evening hours and gatherings. This risk was mitigated by adult supervision during outdoor activities in the city.

11.7.5.5 *User Experience*

Participants/students/pupils showed a high level of engagement during lectures, site visits, games and social events.

11.7.5.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

Several social events (dinners, social games, lectures) provided opportunities for social interaction. This demonstration activity acted as an important meeting point for students from different partner countries (from Denmark, Finland, Greece, Serbia and Spain) to meet and exchange ideas, allowing them to share different cultural perspectives.

11.8 Pilot Partner Citizens (EU)

11.8.1 Demonstrator Activity *Open Innovation* (written by AGO)

11.8.1.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The Open Innovation challenge required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) Set up of a dedicated GreenSCENT platform powered by AGO's innovation management software.

AGO's innovation management software existed and has been used to organise Open Innovation programmes for decades.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: high.

The Open Innovation challenge required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) visualisation machines (computer, screen) for showing the educational material;
- (2) computers to work on the deliverable to be uploaded on the platform.

All of these tools have existed in their basic form for decades.

11.8.1.2

Implementation Statistics

In total, three open innovation programmes have been launched as part of the GreenSCENT project. Two of them were designed to address young EU citizens enrolled in European Universities and schools, and the third one was designed to address entrepreneurs and European SMEs.

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in:

- (1) M14–M19 (First Open Innovation Challenge, called “Sustainable Food Challenge 2023”);
- (2) M22–M30 (Second Open Innovation Challenge, called “Farm to Fork – Student Track”);
- (3) M22–M30 (Third Open Innovation Challenge, called “Farm to Fork – Startup Track”).

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was:

- (1) 6 months (First Open Innovation Challenge);
- (2) 9 months (Second Open Innovation Challenge);
- (3) 8 months (Third Open Innovation Challenge).

The number of participants for the First Open Innovation Challenge (Student Track – 2023) was (more details are provided in D2.3 and D5.2):

- (1) 668 participants split in 241 teams;
- (2) 104 projects participated at the start and 100 projects completed;
- (3) 447 citizens were involved in the public voting;
- (4) 4 finalists selected to pitch at final event in Paris.

The number of participants for the Second Open Innovation Challenge (Student Track – 2024) was:

- (1) 1067 participants split in 468 teams;
- (2) 233 projects participated at the start and 199 projects completed;
- (3) 3324 citizens were involved in the public voting;
- (4) 4 finalists selected to pitch at final event in Brussels.

The number of participants for the Second Open Innovation Challenge (Startup Track – 2024) was:

- (1) 98 participants;
- (2) 65 projects participated at the start and 55 projects completed;
- (3) 2 external industry partners were involved;
- (4) 4 finalists selected to pitch at final event in Brussels.

11.8.1.3 Ethical Questions

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.8.1.4 Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.8.1.5 User Experience

The user experience of the Open Innovation challenges under the GreenSCENT project focused on ensuring participant engagement and satisfaction. Key aspects included the following:

- (1) **Platform Usability:** The GreenSCENT platform was intuitive and easy to navigate. We received very few questions about the use of the platform via the administrator chat. The external industry partners also provided very positive feedback on the voting functionality which enabled them to browse through the projects received, and to assess those based on the criteria provided.
- (2) **Support and Resources:** Deliverable templates for the Powerpoint presentation and the one-pager, which were required from the student teams, were easily accessible at all time on the challenge page, aiding participants in effectively developing their projects. In addition, the FAQ and dedicated support team was available to give feedback to participants.
- (3) **Engagement Activities:** Regular updates sent through the communication module of the platform kept participants motivated and engaged. The highlights were the final event in Paris in July

2023 and the final event in Brussels in June 2024. The final events were pitching sessions, during which participants presented their project in front of the audience, and were offered valuable feedback from teachers, researchers and industry experts.

11.8.1.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

During the Student Track of the Open Innovation challenges, citizens could create interdisciplinary and intercultural teams to work on their project. The following cultures/countries were represented in the implementation of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site:

- (1) first Open Innovation Challenge: 42 countries represented, from which 57% were European;
- (2) second Open Innovation Challenge: 45 countries represented, from which 58% were European;
- (3) third Open Innovation Challenge: 40 countries represented, from which 50% were European.

The following sectoral areas came together in the implementation of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site:

- (1) Students from higher education (participants of the Student Track);
- (2) Startup and SME owners (participants of the Startup Track);
- (3) Mentors from the consortium (Democracy X, CSRC);
- (4) Professors (AGO partner professors, who used the challenges as part of their curriculum);
- (5) Corporates (sponsors of the Startup Track).

The cross-cultural impact of open innovation programmes is significant, as evidenced by the diverse participation in the three Open Innovation challenges. With participants from over 40 countries in each iteration, with a significant representation from Europe, these programmes foster interdisciplinary and intercultural collaboration. The involvement of students, startup owners, mentors, professors and corporate sponsors from different cultural and professional backgrounds has clearly enriched the innovation process. This diversity has facilitated a rich exchange of ideas, highlighting the positive influence of cross-cultural interactions in driving innovative solutions.

11.8.2 *Demonstrator Activity CleanAir@Schools (written by 4S)*

11.8.2.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

CleanAir@Schools required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) Air quality sensors: Palmes diffusion tubes;
- (2) CleanAir@Schools web interface;
- (3) CleanAir@Schools mobile application.

The air quality sensors existed and have been used for measuring air quality for decades. The CleanAir@Schools web interface was developed during the project and the mobile application was improved and adapted to the educational sector during the project. Please note that the activity is open to a less technological demand replacing or supporting points (2) and (3) with paper-based maps and paper deployment sheets.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

CleanAir@Schools required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) visual equipment (computer, screen) to display the educational material;
- (2) computers to work on the mapping of the monitoring sites (web interface);
- (3) tablets or smartphones to collect metadata (mobile application).

All of these tools have existed in their basic form for many years or decades.

11.8.2.2

Implementation Statistics

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in:

- (1) M22–M23 (first campaign),
- (2) M26–M27 (second campaign).

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was approximately 8–10 weeks, broken down as follows:

- (1) between one and two hours to read the learning materials and activity guides;
- (2) an internal tutoring session to explain to the students what the task consists of and choose among all the most suitable points to measure pollution in the school environment;
- (3) two days dedicated field trips: one day to place the sensors, and another day, approximately four weeks later, to remove them (about 3 hours per day);
- (4) a final tutoring session to comment on the results and to discuss what can be done to improve them.

The number of participants was as follows:

First campaign.

- | | | | |
|-----|------------|-------------|---------------|
| (1) | Girona: | 10 schools, | 500 students; |
| (2) | Barcelona: | 7 schools, | 350 students; |

(3) Basauri: 15 schools, 500 students.

Second campaign:

(1) Girona: 5 schools, 250 students;

(2) Barcelona and Vic: 9 schools, 450 students;

(3) Etxebarri-Galdakao : 3 schools, 150 students

(4) Madrid: 7 schools, 350 students;

(5) Terrassa: 7 schools, 350 students;

(6) Salt : 2 schools, 100 students;

(7) Sarria, Galicia: 1 school, 50 students.

Note: All activities took place in schools in Spain.

11.8.2.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.8.2.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.8.2.5 *User Experience*

The CleanAir@Schools activity is firmly rooted in the school curriculum as it integrates relevant material into existing subjects by creating interesting activities. Subjects such as science, geography, biology, skills labs, as well as extracurricular activities such as TEDx and Young Scientists groups, lend themselves to discussions about air pollution and hands-on activities that allow students to observe and understand air pollution and its effects on human health and the environment.

The CleanAir@Schools activity promoted an interdisciplinary approach by incorporating elements not only of the above subjects, but also of mathematics and even art through maps and posters so that students could communicate their findings. The activity offers an engaging educational experience, promoting awareness and understanding of air quality issues and encouraging proactive measures to improve the environment.

The key aspects include the following points.

- (1) **Educational and support materials.** Teachers were provided with detailed presentations, activity guides and educational support units that outline the goals, activities and expected outcomes of the CleanAir@Schools project. These plans include background information on air quality, step-by-step instructions for each activity and suggested discussion points.
- (2) **Platform and application usability.** The CleanAir@Schools platform and mobile app feature intuitive interfaces designed for

ease of use. Clear instructions and streamlined navigation ensure that participants can quickly access the tools and resources they need. The platform and app integrate seamlessly, allowing for easy data collection and real-time monitoring. Participants can easily log data, visualize results and track progress.

- (3) **Results Report.** The report is designed to be user-friendly, comprehensive, and actionable. It provides a clear overview of results, detailed data presentation, and in-depth analysis, along with practical recommendations and resources for continued learning and advocacy.
- (4) **Support and Resources.** A dedicated team provided technical support and troubleshooting assistance. Participants could access help via chat, email or phone to resolve issues quickly.
- (5) **Ongoing Learning and Other Resources.** Ongoing activities and projects offered as optional educational units allowed participants to continue learning after the measurement project phase. They remained involved in air quality monitoring and kept abreast of environmental changes.

11.8.2.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

The CleanAir@Schools activity has the potential to have a profound cross-cultural impact by promoting environmental awareness, fostering collaboration and advocating for equity. By connecting students and teachers around the world, the project builds a diverse and united front against air pollution, driving positive change in communities.

CleanAir@Schools' cross-cultural measurement includes standardized data collection methods, adaptable educational materials, comparative analysis, contextual interpretation, inclusive participation, collaborative projects, culturally sensitive reporting and impact assessment. This comprehensive approach ensures that the project effectively addresses and respects cultural diversity while promoting global environmental awareness and action.

11.8.3 *Demonstrator Activity Youth Design Assemblies (written by Democracy X)*

11.8.3.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: medium.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: medium.

The pilot required the following technologies for its implementation:

- (1) Wi-Fi connection;
- (2) laptops or PCs;
- (3) mobile phones;
- (4) screen and projector.

All these technologies and appliances are regularly used by almost all young people in Europe.

11.8.3.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M10–M25.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 12 days.

The number of participants was: 56.

The four YDAs were attended by 56 participants aged between 14 and 25 years from seven European countries: Denmark, Finland, Greece, Italy, Romania, Serbia and Spain. Initially, a number of 58 participants had joined the YDAs, but two withdrew during the 15 months of the activity. Approximately 55 percent were male, 43 percent female and 2 percent identified as other. Each of the four YDAs had 2 participants from each country, with a few exceptions. The occupational status of the participants ranged from primary school, through high school, to university students and recent graduates.

The implementation of the YDA demonstrator activity took place online a total of 7 times, in 4 different groups. One additional instance took place physically in the cities of Barcelona (Spain), Copenhagen (Denmark), Novi Sad (Serbia) and Rome (Italy); this face-to-face version is considered and described here in the report as a pilot activity.

11.8.3.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.8.3.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24).

The specific risks identified for this activity related to the safety of the YDA participants in the cities of Novi Sad and Barcelona during evening hours. This risk was mitigated by adult supervision during outdoor activities in the city.

11.8.3.5 *User Experience*

Each of the four YDAs met a total of eight times for eight different workshops, seven of which were conducted online and the last in the four European cities (Section 11.8.3.2). The face-to-face workshop is considered here as a pilot activity, while the other 7 are considered as demonstrators. The participating young people, aged between 14 and 25, were given the opportunity to influence the design and implementation of the different technologies and frameworks developed within the GreenSCENT project.

For example, during the workshops, participants co-created ideas on how to use the developed applications in educational settings and helped to design the resulting prototypes. A later workshop then followed up on how these ideas were taken up by the project partners, leading one participant to state that “seeing the results [i.e., the implementation of the co-created insights] made me feel that I had contributed to the start of

a greener Europe.” The structure of eight workshops thus allowed participants to gain a sense of empowerment by experiencing that their voices were actually heard throughout the activity.

The addition of an in-person workshop to complement the online workshops ensured even more community building than was possible through the online versions alone. Here, the participating young people manifested a sense of contributing to the green transition with their peers, solidifying the bubbling interests that led them to participate in the pilot activity in the first place.

From the statements made by participants in the final workshop, it is clear that the YDAs have motivated many participants to take part in the Green Deal transition. The YDAs thus achieved their goal of being a catalyst for action.

11.8.3.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

This demonstrator activity acted as an important meeting point for students from different partner countries, allowing them to share different cultural perspectives. It also fostered the sense of community that comes from working with like-minded people to create a more sustainable future.

11.9 Updates

11.9.1 Update on Section 11.8.2 (Demonstrator Activity *CleanAir@Schools* for Citizens (EU)): *CleanAir@Schools* implementation at schools in Copenhagen, Denmark (written by 4S)

The *CleanAir@Schools* initiative was to be piloted in Copenhagen, Denmark, with the aim of involving local schools in monitoring air quality and educating students about the environmental and health impacts of air pollution. Partner organisation Democracy X invited in May 2024 two schools to participate, one primary school and one secondary school. A total of 100 students from these schools were initially registered to take part in the activity.

Despite significant efforts by 4S and Democracy X in terms of communication and logistical support, the engagement with the schools proved challenging:

- (1) **Limited participation.** Of the two schools invited, only the primary school partially participated, using only half of the provided materials and involving only one of the two classes originally enrolled.
- (2) **Non-participation.** The secondary school did not carry out the activity at all, despite prior commitments. 4S and Democracy X teams were not informed of the decision or the impossibility of carrying out the activity.
- (3) **Communication problems.** Communication with both schools was difficult throughout the process. Attempts to establish consistent contact and gather feedback were largely unsuccessful, resulting in a lack of cooperation and responsiveness from the schools.

The pilot was also hampered by logistical problems:

- (1) **Unreturned materials.** Activity materials provided to schools were not returned, preventing recycling and closure of the pilot. This affected the ability to reallocate or re-use resources for other potential participants.
- (2) **Lack of feedback.** A report summarising the activity and initial findings was produced by 4S and sent to the contact point at the partially participating school. However, despite several follow-ups, no feedback or acknowledgement was received.

As a result of these communication barriers and lack of engagement, the 4S and Democracy X teams ultimately decided in October 2024 to discontinue further attempts to engage with the schools. The decision was made to avoid spending further resources on an unresponsive audience. The CleanAir@Schools pilot project in Copenhagen serves as a learning experience about the importance of school engagement and the challenges that can arise in collaborative educational projects.

11.9.2 Update on Section 11.5.6 (Demonstrator Activity *GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App* implemented at RGSMART)

The number of participants reported in D5.3 missed the number of students; the updated version here (Section 11.5.6.2) has them included (an increase by 240 persons).

11.9.3 Update on Section 11.8 (Demonstrator Activity *GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App* for Citizens (EU)) (written by BSC)

The specific implementation of this demonstrator activity is called *GreenAir App*. It was carried out in spring and autumn 2024. It is described in detail in D3.5.

11.9.3.1 *Technology Relevance*

The relevance of the technology for the development of the demonstrator activity is assessed as: high.

The relevance of the technology for the implementation at the pilot site is assessed as: high.

The GreenAir App required the following technologies for its development:

- (1) React framework;
- (2) Babylon.js;
- (3) Figma (for prototyping and testing).

The GreenAir App prioritizes accessibility by using web technologies that allow the application to be used in the web browser of most mobile devices, desktop computers and tablets without the need to install any additional software. All that is required to access the App is an Internet connection. This platform-agnostic design ensures a consistent user experience. The development uses the renowned React framework for a high-performance interface, complemented by Babylon.js for immersive 3D environments. In particular, Babylon.js enables an augmented reality (AR) experience on compatible smartphones (currently excluding Apple iOS), adding interactivity to lessons 3, 7 and 8 (cf. D3.5).

11.9.3.2 *Implementation Statistics*

The implementation of the demonstrator activity happened in: M26 and M31.

The duration of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site was: 3 days.

The number of participants was: 134

thereof:

- | | | |
|-----|-----------|------|
| (1) | teachers: | 4; |
| (2) | students: | 130. |

There were a total of four different groups in Barcelona, Spain, that carried out the pilot activity. In May 2024, the British College of Gavà, Spain, conducted a piloting session, which involved 40 students. This early session, held before the consortium's second round of piloting, allowed us to implement updates based on student feedback.

At Escola Pia Balmes, Spain, the activities were conducted as part of Matins de Recerca, an initiative that facilitates the integration of research with academic institutions in October 2024. Through this programme, BSC collaborated with the school, where three groups participated and provided constructive feedback. A total of 90 students participated in that activity.

11.9.3.3 *Ethical Questions*

The ethical questions associated with the implementation were as described in D5.2: consent forms and data storage. No other issues arose during the implementation of the demonstrator activity.

11.9.3.4 *Risk and Mitigation Actions: An Update*

In addition to the foreseen and unforeseen risks and mitigation measures as communicated in D5.2 (Table 1 therein), the following issues arose since the completion of D5.2 (M24): none.

11.9.3.5 *User Experience*

The primary demographic utilizing the App are students within the 10 to 15 year age range. The user experience of the application was commended. Students expressed particular enthusiasm for the interactive components, with the AR maps in lessons 7 and 8 identified as the most engaging features. The students found the App visually appealing; however, some recommended incorporating additional images or animations.

The demonstrator team placed significant emphasis on the user experience, with a process of continuous improvement being a core tenet of their approach. All feedback and bug reports from pilot sites are subject to rigorous review and addressed in an appropriate manner. This iterative process ensures the App's effectiveness as a user-friendly learning tool.

It should be noted that all data collected during the pilot testing phase is anonymized in order to safeguard students' privacy. This ensures that honest and unbiased feedback can be gathered without the need for individual consent forms. As the report gathers data throughout the year, it will be continuously updated with anonymized responses from all pilot sites, offering a comprehensive and evolving picture of user experiences.

11.9.3.6 *Cross-Cultural Impact*

The pilot testing phase of the GreenAir App facilitated valuable collaboration between a diverse range of stakeholders, including representatives from educational institutions (school administrators and teachers), research partners (BSC), and university support personnel. This collaborative approach proved beneficial for all parties involved.

11.10 Summary Statistics

Table 3 provides an overview of the number of participants in the demonstrator activities carried out and described in the previous sections (including the updates in Section 11.9).

Table 3. Summary statistics for the number of participants.

# of Participants	13 December 2024 © Climate Risk Analysis										
Pilot Site	Demonstrator										Sum
	Environmental Monitoring App	Citizen Journalism/Greenverse	Interactive Documentary/Greenverse	Microplastic Citizen Science	Open Innovation	Climathon	CleanAir @Schools	GreenSCENT Augmented Reality App	Youth Design Assemblies	Knowledge Graph	
	ENG	ENG	ENG	UAB	AGO	CRA	4S	BSC	Democracy X	UNINETTUNO	
UAB									56		56
EA			12			5	308	152	{4} †		477
MAYK	16										16
RST	66	66	87	22 §			59	86	6		392
RGSMART	5	225	12			20	{53} *	243	4 †		509
UNINETTUNO	9	9	6				81 + 180 = 261 ‡			16	301
UNSPMF			18			27	53 *		23		121
Citizens (EU)					668 + 1067 + 98 = 1833 ‡		1350 + 1650 + 100 = 3100 ‡	134	56		5123
Sum	96	300	135	22	1833	52	3781	615	145	16	6995

Notes: Numerical entries in black are from D5.3; numerical entries in red are from D5.3u (see Section 11.9 therein); the Knowledge Graph is a new (vs. D5.2) demonstrator activity developed by UNINETTUNO;
 *, activity implemented jointly, counted here only once (where not in parentheses);
 †, activity implemented jointly, counted here only once (where not in parentheses);
 ‡, activity implemented more than once, counted here is the sum;
 §, at the Copenhagen project meeting in April 2024, it was resolved by consensus that EA and UNSPMF would not be responsible for implementing this activity, but that RST would assume this role.